

MASTER THESIS

A Qualitative Exploration of How Game Art Students Engage with Art Historical Material

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DECLARATION OF AUTHORSHIP

I, Iza Morel, declare that this thesis titled, "A Qualitative Exploration of How Game Art Students Engage with Art Historical Material" and the work presented are my own. I confirm that:

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A Qualitative Exploration of How Game Art Students Engage with Art Historical Material

During this study I got the opportunity to learn more about research and was able to expand my horizon through increasing my academic understanding and deepening my knowledge. And, more than anything, it reminded me how important it is to stay curious.

Iza Morel

ABSTRACT

Academy for AI, Games and Media

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By Iza Morel

Art history is largely absent from game art curricula, and almost no research has examined whether engaging with it holds value for game artists or their creative practice. This study explored that gap, asking how game art students and recent alumni perceive and make meaning from post-impressionist visual techniques and historical context, and how they relate this encounter to their own creative process and design outcomes. Fifteen semi-structured interviews were conducted with eleven participants, built around a set of paintings the researcher and the participants each chose to look at and discuss together (a method known as visual elicitation), and analysed for recurring themes using Reflexive Thematic Analysis. Three themes were developed: Identity, Engagement, and Practical application. Participants approached the works primarily through their own creative identity, positioning themselves as outsiders to the fine-art world and separating game art from 'real' art on the basis of purpose. Looking slowly and with prompting surfaced responses they did not expect, and vocabulary served as a resource for putting perceptions into words rather than as a measure of how much they noticed. Practical connections, where they appeared, stayed close to the surface and were sometimes bridged by a familiar game that showed a traditional style working digitally. Overall, the encounter held value conditionally rather than uniformly, depending on what each participant brought to it, how it was framed, and their disciplinary focus. The findings offer a first mapping of an under-researched intersection and identify the conditions that warrant further study.

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The researcher acknowledges the use of a large language model (Claude, by Anthropic, used under a BUAs data-processing agreement, with the Sonnet and Opus models) in accordance with BUAs' Level 5 AI guidelines. The tool was used for feedback, proofreading, and grammar and editing support, and at times for translation between the researcher's native language (Dutch) and English.

After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited all content as needed and takes full responsibility and ownership of the conceptualisation and content of this thesis.

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To my parents, brother, family and friends for their endless support

1 INTRODUCTION

How important is art historical knowledge, particularly the history of painting, for game artists? This question arose during the researcher's bachelor's programme in game art, prompted by the realisation that formal education in the history of painting, or any art history, had not been part of the curriculum. The absence of this foundation felt like a missing piece in artistic development. Conversations with classmates revealed that this concern was widely shared. Many expressed a sense of having missed out on potentially crucial elements that could enrich the creative process.

Through conversations with fellow students and lecturers, specific limitations became apparent. A common reported observation was using design principles, such as compositional rules or colour theory, without understanding their origins or theoretical foundations. Some mentioned struggling to use traditional paintings as inspiration, lacking the knowledge to understand and apply historical techniques. And, perhaps most troubling, some recognised an 'echo chamber', drawing inspiration exclusively from contemporary game art without understanding its deeper roots. This self-referential cycle, where game artists only study other game artists, potentially limits visual innovation in the field.

Research confirmed that art historical knowledge benefits creative students. Greene et al. (2014) demonstrated that museum exposure significantly improved students' critical thinking skills and artistic interest. More recently, Bara et al. (2025) found that art knowledge training changed how people made aesthetic judgments, suggesting that historical understanding actively shaped visual perception. If game art programmes omit this art historical training, students may miss out on these documented cognitive and creative benefits.

It was also wondered whether this gap in the curriculum was unique to the researcher's own institution. Through desk research, it was discovered that art history receives minimal attention in game studies curricula worldwide, as documented in Tunnel and Norbistrath's (2023) comprehensive analysis. Furthermore, there was virtually no literature that examined how art history might benefit game artists specifically. Winner et al. (2013) noted, in general terms, that "there is far too little research on the impact of arts education on student outcomes," while Murray (2020) specifically speaks of a "critical and methodological deadlock" between art history and game studies, suggesting that these fields struggle to communicate effectively with one another, which may contribute to the lack of interdisciplinary research in this area.

The personal observations and findings of the initial desk research described above raised multiple questions: What perceived effects does art historical knowledge have on game art students? Which of the many art historical movements would most benefit game artists? Do the effects differ per game art discipline, such as character design versus environment art? Faced with this broad possibility space, and given the duration of the one-year master's programme, it was decided to scope the study down to exploratory research within a specific art-historical framework, namely that of post-impressionism. The main research question was the following:

How do game art students and recent alumni perceive and make meaning from post-impressionist visual techniques and historical context, and how do they relate this encounter to their creative process and design outcomes?

Post-impressionism was selected as the starting point for investigating the potential role of art history in game art education because the distinctive features of this movement, such as

expressive brushstrokes, bold colour choices, and interpretive rather than literal representation, align with some of the stylised visuals common in game art. Post-impressionists like Van Gogh and Cézanne experimented with ways to convey emotion and atmosphere through visual distortion, which parallels the way game artists create atmosphere and guide players' attention. Through a small-scale exploratory qualitative study, drawing on in-depth semi-structured interviews built around a visual elicitation method, it explored how game art students and recent alumni perceived and made meaning from an encounter with post-impressionist visual techniques, underlying theories, and historical context, and how they related that encounter to their own creative practice.

Two areas of potential influence this study sought to explore were: whether such encounters shape how students articulate their design decisions, including their use of vocabulary and historical references; and whether exposure to art historical material outside the typical game art reference pool might broaden participants' sense of their own creative possibilities. Given the qualitative nature of this research, the emphasis lies less on confirming or denying potential influence than on gathering preliminary insights that may provide direction for future research and potential curricular considerations.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

The introduction revealed that art history was notably absent from game art curricula, starting with the researcher's own programme and extending to a broader question: how common is this gap across European game art education? The hypothesis emerged that incorporating art history could offer various benefits to game artists' development. This led to the central research question exploring the potential relationship between art history and game art students.

This chapter started investigating the research question through systematic desk research, following a clear progression. It begins with an inventory of European game art programs to map where art history appears (or does not) in current curricula. The discussion then shifts to existing literature on art history's educational benefits, including the existing pedagogical approach Visual Thinking Strategies (VTS) (Yenawine, 2013). The chapter then introduces and defines the concept of art historical literacy, before extending this framework with the notion of meaning-making. The investigation then turns to what existing research suggests about the relationship between art knowledge and creative practice, considering both knowledge transfer literature and design cognition research. The chapter concludes by explaining the selection of post-impressionism as the focal art movement for this research, providing both practical and theoretical justification for this choice.

2.1 THE PRESENCE OF ART HISTORY IN EUROPEAN GAME ART CURRICULA

2.1.1 Games in art history education

Before examining what game art programmes currently teach, it is worth noting that the reverse relationship, using games to teach art history, is more documented and successful.

Multiple studies demonstrate the value of games as pedagogical tools for making art history education more engaging. Hutson et al. (2025) found that their gamified art history curriculum, integrating "global narratives and innovative teaching strategies", significantly improved "student satisfaction, cultural openness, and engagement with global art."

The quasi-experimental study by Mohd Bakhir et al. (2025) with 40 college students compared digital game-based learning versus traditional instruction over one month, finding that digital games were effective for enhancing both art knowledge and art interest. Additionally, Ćosović and Brkić's (2019) systematic literature review of game-based learning in cultural heritage and museum contexts found that game-based approaches increased motivation and engagement, provided instant feedback, and enhanced creativity.

While these studies demonstrate the effectiveness of games in teaching art history, the reverse relationship, using art history to enhance game art education, remains unexplored. This study sought to investigate whether the positive effects observed in one direction might also apply in reverse.

2.1.2 Game Art curricula

Understanding what game art programmes currently teach establishes the baseline of our participants and gives perspective on how common this lack of art history integration into teaching might be. Peer-reviewed literature on the role of art history in game art curricula remains scarce. Tunnel and Norbistrath's (2023) study analysing curricula in European Games Bachelor's programmes provides substantial data but makes no mention of art history. Therefore, the following analysis relies primarily on programme descriptions from the educational institutions themselves.

Modern game art curricula appear to cover fundamental visual principles through practical application. Notably, resources exist that teach art principles specifically in the context of game art, such as Solarski's *Drawing Basics and Video Game Art (2013)*. This comprehensive guide includes dedicated chapters on perspective, anatomy, composition and colour theory, teaching traditional art principles in a game-specific context. The book studies classical artists (Michelangelo, Titian, Rubens) alongside AAA games, suggesting a recognition of historical relevance.

Despite these resources, game art programmes rarely include dedicated art history content. Technical courses appear to remain the priority. Among the European schools examined for reference, only three explicitly include traditional art history. RUBIKA in France incorporates "histoire de l'art" within cultural education. Uppsala University in Sweden teaches "art history for level design", a framing that appears to be primarily practical; and Howest hogeschool in Belgium mentions "Art history" specifically being part of their course "Foundation for games".

These observations had clear limitations. They relied on public programme descriptions, not detailed syllabi, potentially underrepresenting art historical content taught within other courses. However, this apparent lack of art history in game art curricula aligns with the aforementioned analysis of Tunnel and Norbistrath (2023), which studied 113 European programmes and identified no art history component across the curricula examined. Moreover, the industry-focused IGDA Curriculum Framework (The IGDA Education Special Interest Group (EdSIG), 2008) specified nine core topics: Critical Game Studies, Games and Society, Game Design, Game Programming, Visual Design, Audio Design, Interactive Storytelling, Game Production and Business of Gaming without any mention or inclusion of art history. The framework actively advocates for interdisciplinary breadth, drawing on fields as varied as computer science, the social sciences, and the humanities; yet art history is absent from its recommendations. This exclusion may suggest a systemic rather than incidental absence and appears to represent an industry-wide assumption about relevance, made without much empirical evidence to support it.

2.1.3 Game Industry examples

Despite the absence of formal art historical education in game programmes, several industry examples show the added value of art history already recognised by the games industry. Several documented cases show direct art historical influence.

Figure 2.1 - Screenshot of Cuphead, Studio MDHR Entertainment Inc., 2017

Figure 2.2 - Popeye the Sailor Meets Sindbad the Sailor, Fleischer, 1936

Cuphead's (Studio MDHR Entertainment Inc., 2017) explicit inspiration comes from 1930s animation. The Moldenhauers stated: "We tested out a few story-book and cartoon styles but kept coming back to the rubber-hose animation of the 30's. ... The core of Cuphead's aesthetic matches closest with the Fleischer Brothers' work" (Couture, 2018). The Fleischer brothers, best known for Betty Boop, Popeye, and Koko the Clown, used the rubber-hose animation style characterised by fluid, bendy limbs and surreal transformations. Their distinctive visual style directly influenced Cuphead's aesthetic nearly a century later. See figures 2.1 and 2.2 above.

Figure 2.3 - Screenshot of Ōkami HD, CAPCOM Co., Ltd, 2017

Figure 2.4 - Survivor, Sato, 1995

The designers of Ōkami (Clover Studio, 2006) described purposefully pivoting from their original realistic style to a Japanese-inspired aesthetic: "one day a designer was just playing around and drew a Japanese-style Amaterasu and with that, we abandoned the realistic style." (shmuplations, 2004). They drew inspiration from historical Japanese art forms including Ukiyo-e (Japanese woodblock prints) and sumi-e (ink wash painting). See figures 2.3 and 2.4 above.

Figure 2.5 - Screenshot from Monument Valley, ustwo Games, 2022

Figure 2.6 - Waterfall, Escher, 1961

Monument Valley (ustwo games, 2022) was mechanically rather than visually inspired by the impossible geometries of M.C. Escher (see figures 2.5 and 2.6 above). The developer stated: “I have always wanted to make a game about architecture, and during these sessions I came across Ascending and Descending by M.C. Escher. That gave me the idea for guiding a character from the bottom of a building to the top.” (Creative Bloq Staff, 2014). Although Escher’s characteristic black and white sketch style was not directly adopted, the game focused on the mathematical aspects of Escher’s work, particularly the impossible staircases that inspired the game’s puzzle mechanics.

Figure 2.7 - Screenshot from The Master's Pupil, Pat Naoum Games, 2023

Figure 2.8 - Waterloo Bridge, London, at Sunset, Monet, 1904

The Master’s Pupil (Pat Naoum Games, 2023) draws direct and literal inspiration from Monet’s paintings (see figures 2.7 and 2.8 above). The game is described as “A hand-drawn puzzle-adventure game where you explore the eye and life of master artist Claude Monet. You’ll complete puzzles based upon physics, space, and colour and assist one of the fathers of impressionism as he perseveres through personal hardship, loss, and health difficulties.” (Pat Naoum Games, 2023). The game aims to help players explore the life and works of Claude Monet and gain an understanding of how his art evolved throughout his life. This is a particularly literal industry application of Monet’s impressionistic visual style in a game context.

These examples demonstrate traceable connections between art history and game aesthetics that exist in practice despite their absence from formal education and research. Bourgonjon et al. (2017) described the lack of literature as “blind spots both from the world of art as well as from the field of games studies. Scholars are preoccupied with the dominant approaches and

perspectives in the fields they are trained in, which can make them blind to other potentially interesting perspectives.”

2.2 WHAT WE KNOW ABOUT THE EFFECT OF ART HISTORY ON STUDENTS

Multiple studies demonstrate the positive effects of including art history in educational contexts. Greene et al.'s (2014) experimental study with 3,811 students examined the effects of museum field trips to Crystal Bridges Museum. Students showed significant improvements in critical thinking skills, increased tolerance and empathy, and greater interest in art museums, with effects maintained at follow-up assessment. The follow-up study by Kisida et al. (2016) built upon this previous work and validated the previous findings. It confirmed critical thinking improvements, with students better able to make inferences from images and demonstrating enhanced visual analysis and interpretation skills.

Additionally, Eisner (2002) argued that arts education develops unique cognitive abilities, including the capacity to perceive subtle qualities, construct meaning from ambiguous forms, and recognize multiple solutions to problems. This suggests that an encounter with art historical material could influence both aesthetic judgment and creative problem-solving.

An existing pedagogical framework that addresses the impact of art exposure on students comes from Visual Thinking Strategies (VTS), developed by Abigail Housen and Philip Yenawine, which emphasised prolonged, dialogic looking through open questions such as “What’s going on here?” and “What do you see that makes you say that?” (Yenawine, 2013). VTS draws on Housen’s (2002) research on aesthetic development, which holds that sustained engagement with art, supported by facilitated dialogue, plays a meaningful role in how viewers come to perceive and interpret what they see. Its distinctive claim is that meaning-making is cultivated through dialogue and slow looking rather than through information delivery alone. This insight, together with the open questions developed within VTS, informed the design of the visual elicitation methodology used in this study (detailed in Chapter 3).

However, Ludwig and Boyle’s (2017) systematic review for the Wallace Foundation, which examined 135 reports with 27 studies meeting rigorous design criteria under the Every Student Succeeds Act framework, found that “the average effect found in the 27 well-designed and well-implemented studies (i.e., studies meeting the design criteria for Tiers I–III) was statistically significant but modest in magnitude”. This finding of modest effects is crucial for setting realistic expectations for our intervention, significant educational impacts in creative domains typically manifest as incremental rather than transformative changes. These studies provided proof of concept for improving art understanding through education, but they only address half the equation relevant to our context. They measured whether students could better understand existing art, not whether they could apply that understanding to their own work.

2.3 DEFINING ART HISTORICAL LITERACY

In academic literature, literacy rarely has a single, fixed definition. The Cambridge Dictionary defines literacy as: “the ability to read and write/knowledge of a particular subject, or a particular type of knowledge”. Read (2015), however, notes that academic literacy has developed from multiple disciplinary perspectives and can encompass both written and spoken language, though exact boundaries remain unclear.

To provide a conceptual framework for understanding the domain this study investigates, this section defines art historical literacy as it will be used in the analytical phase of this research.

In this research, the term 'art historical literacy' was used to synthesise three distinct but connected literacies: visual literacy, historical literacy, and aesthetic literacy. Each component addressed a different aspect of understanding art within its historical context. Art historical literacy encompassed the ability to visually analyse artworks using formal vocabularies (derived from visual literacy), situate artistic processes within historical and cultural contexts (drawn from historical literacy), and understand and apply theoretical frameworks that drove artistic movements (stemming from aesthetic literacy).

2.3.1 Visual literacy

The term 'visual literacy' was first used as early as 1939 by R.T. Davis (Peña & Dobson, 2021), but it was John L. Debes who is credited with systematising the concept in 1969. His definition, "a group of vision-competencies a human being can develop by seeing and at the same time having and integrating other sensory experiences", aligns with broader definitions of literacy in that it refers to a specific skillset.

Contemporary scholarship has moved beyond the initial framework of Debes. Serafini (2017) emphasises that there is no single definitive definition of visual literacy. Current perspectives define it as "a process of generating meanings in transaction with multimodal ensembles" rather than just a set of cognitive skills. Visual literacy now spans multiple disciplines, including art history and pedagogy (Avgerinou & Ericson, 1997).

The Association of College and Research Libraries established the most widely adopted definition in their Visual Literacy Competency Standards for Higher Education. Visual literacy is "a set of abilities that enables an individual to effectively find, interpret, evaluate, use, and create images and visual media" and encompasses understanding "the contextual, cultural, ethical, aesthetic, intellectual, and technical components involved in the production and use of visual materials." A visually literate individual serves as both "a critical consumer of visual media and a competent contributor to a body of shared knowledge and culture."

In the definition of art historical literacy used in this study, visual literacy represented the ability to interpret, evaluate and use visual elements, understanding how line, colour, composition and form create meaning beyond written or spoken words.

One further distinction shapes how visual literacy is understood in this study and recurs in the analysis. (Polanyi, 1966) argues that practitioners often know more than they can explicitly articulate, with significant knowledge operating below the level of formal language. This concept, often referred to as tacit knowledge, suggests that the presence or absence of formal vocabulary may not reliably indicate the presence or absence of visual understanding, since practitioners may perceive distinctions they cannot easily name. (Schön, 1983) extends this argument specifically to design practice, describing the "knowing-in-action" through which practitioners make competent judgements without being able to articulate the rules underlying them. The analytical consequence for this study was that observational behaviours such as gesture, hesitation, or comparison between images, along with metaphorical or informal language, may carry interpretive weight equal to formal vocabulary. The absence of art historical terms in a participant's transcripts should therefore not be read, by default, as an absence of visual understanding.

2.3.2 Historical literacy

Historical literacy is mostly referred to as historical thinking and has been defined by Wineburg (2001) as “a way of knowing, a method for developing an understanding about the relationships of peoples and events in the past”.

Historical literacy does not require an encyclopaedic knowledge of historical facts from every era or global location (Wineburg, 2001). Such breadth of knowledge is not possessed even by historians and should not be the ultimate aim of history instruction. Instead, historical literacy implies the possession of the skill set necessary to read, reason, write, and learn with historical evidence. Factual and conceptual knowledge both support the development of historical literacy, and in turn, engaging in historical literacy practices helps expand factual and conceptual understanding (Nokes, 2011).

As part of art historical literacy, historical literacy represented the ability to understand artworks within their historical and cultural context, recognising how their era had influenced artists and their work.

2.3.3 Aesthetic literacy

Aesthetic literacy, as defined by Girod et al. (2003), involves “the ability to perceive, interpret, and evaluate aesthetic qualities in both art and everyday experiences.” It encompasses understanding formal aesthetic theories, recognizing different aesthetic philosophies, and applying aesthetic criteria to evaluate and create works. Unlike visual literacy’s focus on decoding visual elements, aesthetic literacy addresses the philosophical and theoretical frameworks that inform artistic movements, understanding not just what artists created, but why they made specific aesthetic choices and how those choices reflected broader cultural and philosophical positions.

D’Olimpio (2022) frames aesthetic literacy in complementary terms, as a skill set that enables learners to make meaning from artworks by drawing on “formal, aesthetic, historical and technical knowledge.” It adds a dimension Girod’s definition leaves implicit: that aesthetic literacy also involves cultivating an open, receptive mode of perception that prepares a viewer to engage with a work rather than only to analyse it. Within art historical literacy, aesthetic literacy therefore represented the capacity to engage with the reasoning underlying artistic movements, understanding the aesthetic logic behind artists’ choices rather than only their visual surface.

2.3.4 Meaning-making

The preceding sections defined art historical literacy as a combination of three competencies: visual, historical, and aesthetic literacy. This definition provided analytical context for understanding the domain this study investigated. However, the competencies associated with the different literacies alone do not fully capture what this research examined. The research question asked how participants made meaning from their encounters with post-impressionist art, a process that extended beyond possessing knowledge or skills.

While the preceding literacies described competencies individuals may bring to encounters with art, meaning-making addressed the process through which individuals actually constructed understanding from those encounters. Kegan (1982, 1994 as cited in Ignelzi, 2000) argues that humans actively construct their own sense of reality rather than passively receiving information. As Ignelzi (2000) summarises, “an event does not have a particular

solitary meaning attached that simply gets transferred to the individual. Instead, meaning is created between the event and the individual's reaction to it."

This constructivist perspective had important implications for this study. If meaning is individually constructed, then the same post-impressionist painting may hold different significance for different participants depending on their prior experiences, existing frameworks, and current creative processes. This reinforced the case for qualitative inquiry into individual perception and interpretation rather than assuming or researching uniform effects.

For the purposes of this research, meaning-making referred to the active process through which participants constructed personal understanding and significance from their encounters with post-impressionist artworks and contextual information. This concept was central to the research question, which asked not whether participants learned specific content but how they perceived and made meaning from the artworks they encountered during the study.

2.4 WHAT RESEARCH SUGGESTS ABOUT ART KNOWLEDGE AND CREATIVE PRACTICE

2.4.1 Knowledge transfer literature

Bara et al. (2025) show that art knowledge training changes how individuals make aesthetic judgments about artworks of the kind studied, with enhanced pattern recognition and contextual understanding offered as the underlying mechanism. However, this does not indicate whether such training changes how people create art. It shows a connection between increased knowledge about a subject and enhanced aesthetic judgment, but it does not prove a definitive link between having higher literacy and being able to apply it to one's own creative process. This section explores whether theoretical knowledge can meaningfully influence or transfer into creative production, based on available evidence.

Research into knowledge transfer within creative disciplines shows mixed results. The taxonomic framework developed by Barnett and Ceci (2002) identifies nine dimensions for understanding near and far transfer of knowledge including: learned skill, performance change, memory demands as content dimensions; and knowledge domain, physical context, temporal context, functional context, social context, and modality as context dimensions. These dimensions help clarify what type of transfer is being measured and under what conditions transfer is most likely to occur. Their analysis indicates that near transfer within similar contexts receives stronger empirical support than far transfer across distinct domains. These findings are supported by meta-analyses conducted by Sala and Gobet (2017), which investigated transfer effects across various domains. Their research shows that far transfer between unrelated fields is rare, whereas near transfer within similar domains tends to produce more consistent and positive outcomes. Their analysis of chess studies, music education, and video game training revealed that transfer effects were strongest when source and target domains share substantial structural similarities, a condition that arguably exists between traditional art principles and digital game art.

Lastly, Christiaans and Venselaar (2005) found a correlation between creativity and process knowledge, defined as the ability to manage the design process. Their study reported that students with greater process knowledge produced more creative designs, suggesting that enhanced knowledge correlates with more creative outcomes. Although the focus of this

research is not to test or improve art historical knowledge, this principle of knowledge influencing creativity could potentially extend to an art historical encounter influencing the participants knowledge and understanding, and therefore might influence the process and outcomes of game art students.

2.4.2 How design training shapes perception

Closely related to the question of transfer is the question of what practitioners already bring to encounters with visual material. Lawson (2005) and Cross (2011) argue, respectively, that design education does not simply transfer technical skills but cultivates characteristic ways of attending to and evaluating visual work. These ways of looking distinguish designers' judgements from those of non-designers and are sustained over time by the professional community. What designers notice, what they treat as a problem, and what they treat as a solution become durable cognitive patterns shaped by the discipline they trained in.

In the context of this study, this implied that game art practitioners do not encounter art historical material as blank receivers but through patterns of attention their training has cultivated. These patterns may shape both what registers during the encounter and how participants relate it to their own work. This informed the inclusion of participant-selected images (detailed in Chapter 3), allowing participants' existing visual references to surface rather than only their reactions to the unfamiliar material.

What individuals bring to encounters with cultural material comes not just from design cognition but also from sociology. Bourdieu (1984) argues that the capacity to engage with art is neither evenly distributed nor purely innate, but shaped by what he termed 'cultural capital': the familiarity, dispositions, and competencies accumulated through upbringing, education, and social environment. Where Lawson (2005) and Cross (2011) describe dispositions cultivated by professional training, Bourdieu (1984) describes dispositions cultivated by a broader social and educational background, and the two do not need to align, since a practitioner may have highly developed design-cognitive patterns yet little prior exposure to art history. This distinction mattered here because participants arrived with markedly different relationships to art outside their training (detailed in Chapter 4), and 'cultural capital' offered a way to better understand that variation without reducing it to talent or interest.

Design research has also identified a cognitive constraint relevant to whether external inputs can shift creative practice. Jansson and Smith (1991) describe design fixation as the tendency for designers, once exposed to particular reference examples, to have difficulty generating ideas outside the pattern those examples establish. Goldschmidt (2011) argues that abstraction from such references can mitigate fixation, allowing source material to inform new work without dictating it. While fixation operates at the level of individual cognition, the mechanism is structurally similar to the field-level self-referentiality discussed earlier in this chapter under Game Art curricula: repeated exposure to a particular set of references narrows the space of solutions or styles that feel available. The implication for this study is twofold. On one hand, this literature supports the possibility that art historical material offers value precisely because it sits outside the existing reference pool. On the other, it introduces a caveat consistent with the transfer literature above; whether such material can actually shift creative thinking may depend on whether participants are able to engage with the unfamiliar visuals at a level of abstraction.

2.4.3 Why process matters

The importance of deliberately exploring and discussing the process is based on arguments from creativity research. Sawyer (2012) argues that creativity emerges through the process, not just in outcomes. Social interaction and cultural context also play crucial roles. Focusing solely on final products may overlook significant developments in creative thinking.

The co-evolution model proposed by Dorst and Cross (2001) demonstrates that creative design cannot be understood solely through final artifacts. Their protocol studies of nine industrial designers revealed that creativity emerges through the dynamic interplay between problem and solution spaces, with designers continuously reframing both throughout the process. This finding implies that the encounter may influence how students conceptualize visual problems, even if these changes are not immediately recognizable in outcomes.

The limitations of outcome-focused evaluation are also evident in the study by Wang et al. (2023), where self-regulated learning phases revealed different creativity characteristics at each stage. The planning phase showed divergent thinking, the execution phase demonstrated convergent synthesis, and the reflection phase enabled metacognitive development. This suggests that focusing only on final artifacts may overlook critical creative developments, and that participant reflection on their own process can surface insights not visible in outcomes alone.

The consequence for this research was that attending to participants' perceptions of their creative process, not just their evaluation of artworks, became important. While this study did not directly observe participants creating work, it invited them to reflect on how art historical material might relate to their creative thinking and practice. This reflective approach allowed participants to articulate potential influences on their process.

2.4.4 Absence of literature

Direct transfer between art history and game art remains largely undocumented in peer-reviewed literature. While transfer research provides a theoretical basis for thinking such influence is possible, little empirical evidence has examined whether, or how, it occurs in practice.

This absence of literature in these fields is also noted by Murray (2020), who identifies a "critical and methodological deadlock" between art history and game studies. They state that despite games being predominantly image-based, critical game studies rarely employ art historical methodologies, while art history maintains a "critical neglect of games as legitimate objects of study." Additionally, Martin's (2018) keyword and co-citation analysis of 24,128 game research documents to map out the main areas of game research identifies several disciplinary communities, such as education/culture, computer science or medical fields. But in both keyword and co-citation analysis, art history is missing.

This absence is not merely an academic curiosity but represents a practical gap with potential consequences for game art education. Without empirical investigation, curricular decisions about whether to include art history remain based on assumption rather than evidence. Game art programmes may be omitting potentially valuable content, or alternatively, may be correct in prioritising technical skills but currently, neither position can be substantiated.

2.5 WHY POST-IMPRESSIONISM IS SELECTED AS THE KEY ART HISTORICAL MOVEMENT IN THIS STUDY

This exploratory research employed post-impressionism as its test case, chosen through a combination of personal research interest and practical feasibility. Since no empirical research identified optimal art movements for game art education, movement selection becomes a methodological rather than theoretical decision. This section establishes which features of post-impressionism will be examined during this study while acknowledging the subjective elements in this choice.

Post-impressionism offers several characteristics potentially relevant to game art. Senior 3D artist Shiyan (2025) explains the history of stylization and its current forms, identifying “the essential force” of stylization as a deliberate choice and expression of artistry. The post-impressionist visual abstraction techniques, simplified forms, expressive colour, and symbolic rather than literal representation align with the stylization found in game art.

It should be acknowledged that the selection of any art historical movement as a research focus carries implicit assumptions. Post-impressionism, as a Western European artistic movement, represents specific socio-cultural perspectives of the late 19th century France. While this study uses post-impressionism as a practical starting point for exploratory research, future research might explore whether non-Western art movements offer different insights for game artists, or whether the Eurocentrism of art historical education itself warrants examination.

While theoretical justification for research choices would be preferred, exploratory research “tends to tackle new problems on which little to no previous research has been done.” (Brown, 2006), making a strong theoretical foundation more complex in this case.

The research explored the theoretical applicability of specific post-impressionist principles to game art, acknowledging these are not unique to the movement. Post-impressionist artists appreciated their predecessors but intended to prove they could make their artwork look different and better. Experiments with forms and colours were a way to give a personal touch to paintings and evoke certain emotions in viewers (Wiggins, 1993). Post-impressionism could not be described as a homogeneous movement because it encompassed and was the predecessor of various styles like pointillism popularised by Georges Seurat, fauvism represented by Henri Matisse, or cubism developed by Pablo Picasso and Georges Braque (Swinglehurst, 1995).

Without conclusive sources, the following principles may offer possible theoretical translation to game contexts according to this researcher:

First, expressive brushstrokes or paint application might translate to digital painting techniques or specialised texture creation, as seen in games such as *The Master’s Pupil* (Pat Naoum Games, 2023), directly inspired by Monet, or *Ōkami* (Clover Studio, 2006) with its distinctive Japanese paint-stroke style.

Second, the emphasis of post-impressionists on distortion for expressive effect and use of unnatural colours could inspire game artists to push colour palettes toward greater abstraction and expressiveness. Post-impressionists proved that trees need not be brown and skies need not be blue if other colours better serve the artistic vision.

Third, the geometric reduction and structural simplification in post-impressionism provided potential inspiration for stylisation and abstraction within the game art process or final asset design.

Finally, post-impressionism's emphasis on subjective interpretation over objective representation arguably parallels the mindset of pushing visual styles and game development's emphasis on innovation.

Conversely, all the aforementioned features that make post-impressionism distinctly recognizable can also be valuable when they do not parallel contemporary game art visuals. Encountering unfamiliar visual approaches might prompt participants to observe and articulate more consciously, and might create greater meaning for their own creative processes by drawing attention to features that do not appear as frequently in game art. This reasoning is speculative but did inform the selection of post-impressionism as a test case. Whether such effects occur was explored during this study.

2.6 CHAPTER CONCLUSION

This literature review revealed an interesting paradox. The games industry draws on art historical movements. *Cuphead* borrows from 1930s Fleischer animation (Studio MDHR Entertainment Inc., 2017), *Ōkami* from Ukiyo-e and sumi-e (Clover Studio, 2006), *Monument Valley* from Escher's impossible geometries (ustwo games, 2022), and *The Master's Pupil* engages directly with Monet (Pat Naoum, 2023). Arts education research has shown modest but real effects of visual literacy training (Greene et al., 2014; Ludwig & Boyle, 2017). Yet across both the educational and scholarly landscape, almost no empirical research has explored whether a deliberate encounter with art history holds any relevance for game artists' own practice. This absence runs through several connected layers.

At the level of education, the gap seems structural. Tunnel and Norbistrath's (2023) analysis of 113 European game programmes found no systematic inclusion of art history, and the IGDA Curriculum Framework (The IGDA Education Special Interest Group (EdSIG), 2008) institutionalised this absence even while it advocates for interdisciplinary breadth.

At the scholarly level, the gap seems disciplinary. Murray (2020) identifies a "methodological deadlock" in which art historians rarely study games, and game scholars rarely employ art historical methods. Martin's (2018) analysis of 24,128 game research documents confirms this separation, with art history seemingly absent from interdisciplinary game research.

And at the level of theory, the question of whether art knowledge can inform creative practice at all is still open. Transfer research suggests that moving knowledge between distant domains is hard: far transfer is rare, while near transfer within similar domains shows more promise (Barnett & Ceci, 2002; Sala & Gobet, 2017). Related work links knowledge to creative output (Christiaans and Venselaar, 2005) and art knowledge to shifts in aesthetic judgement (Bara et al., 2025). Whether and how art historical knowledge influences students' own creative processes remains unexplored.

Underlying these gaps sits a point that shaped this study. The reviewed literature on design cognition (Cross, 2011; Lawson, 2005) suggests that practitioners do not encounter visual material as blank receivers but through patterns of attention cultivated by their training, while research on design fixation (Goldschmidt, 2011; Jansson & Smith, 1991) cautioned that exposure can constrain as well as expand creative possibility. Read alongside the constructivist account of meaning-making (Kegan, 1982 as cited in Ignelzi 2000), this positions any encounter between game art practitioners and art historical material as a process shaped by what participants bring with them.

These gaps in literature positioned research at the intersection of art history and game art education as genuinely exploratory territory. Without established theoretical frameworks or validated methodologies, initial investigations focus on better understanding the phenomenon rather than testing predetermined outcomes. Post-impressionism served as a case study for this exploration, chosen through practical and theoretical considerations (explained in 2.5). That this intersection has gone largely unstudied feels like more than an academic oversight. It reflects a possible missed opportunity to enrich creative education through interdisciplinary knowledge.

Whether art history holds meaningful relevance for game art students and their creative practice remains unknown, a gap that both justifies investigation and complicates interpretation of findings. This study aimed to determine whether this intersection merited further investigation, mapping seemingly unexplored territory rather than providing generalizable or conclusive answers. By exploring how an encounter with post-impressionist visual techniques, underlying theories, and historical context relates to game art students' creative process and design outcomes, this study set out to begin addressing a small part of the gap between games and art history.

3 METHODOLOGY

3.1 RESEARCH DESIGN

This study employed a qualitative exploratory research design to investigate how game art students and recent alumni perceive and make meaning from post-impressionist art, and how they relate this encounter to their own creative practices. Through qualitative methods this study focused on the experiences, interpretations and processes of the participants rather than on measurement or frequency. The research sought to understand whether and how art historical encounters may hold relevance for game art practice. The exploratory approach was chosen given the limited existing research on how game art students engage with art historical material, and the need to understand this phenomenon from participants' own perspectives. As exploratory research, this study did not anticipate definitive conclusions. Findings that reveal a limited perceived relevance of art historical encounters for game art students would still be informative, contributing to a better understanding of a relationship that currently lacks empirical investigation.

The study used visual elicitation as its primary data collection method. Visual elicitation is an established qualitative interview technique in which visuals serve as prompts for participant response and discussion, used to elicit deeper thoughts, memories, and experiences that may not be captured through standard interviewing methods (Harper, 2002). Prosser and Loxley (2008) provided a broader overview of image-based research methods across disciplines, and Mannay (2015) examined the application and ethical considerations of visual and creative research methods; both were consulted as methodological references for the design of this study. Rather than relying solely on questions, the use of images served to anchor the conversation and invite participants to articulate their perceptions, interpretations, and associations.

Within the visual elicitation data collection framework, the study employed a combined approach that included both researcher-selected and participant-selected images. Clark-Ibáñez (2004), in particular, highlighted the importance of giving participants a voice within a researcher-driven approach. Each component also served a distinct purpose. Researcher-selected visuals provided control over the research process through the same stimuli for each participant that allowed for cross-participant comparison, while participant-selected images revealed what visual references participants already valued and drew upon in their practice. Furthermore, allowing participants to contribute their own visuals supported a participatory research approach that may minimise power hierarchies between researcher and participant by providing opportunities for participants to exercise agency during the interview (Hatten et al., 2013, as cited in Pearson & Misener, 2024). Details on how the researcher-selected and participant-selected material were obtained are provided in the data collection subchapter (Section 3.4) below. This combined approach allowed exploration of both how participants respond to art historical material and what existing visual frameworks they brought to that encounter.

3.2 RESEARCH QUESTION

The study addressed the following research question:

How do game art students and recent alumni perceive and make meaning from post-impressionist visual techniques and historical context, and how do they relate this encounter to their creative process and design outcomes?

This question was deliberately exploratory, investigating experience, perception, and meaning-making from participants' perspectives rather than measuring effects or testing causal relationships.

3.3 PARTICIPANTS

The participant group consisted of game art students and recent game art alumni, as the research question centred on how this specific population perceived and engaged with art historical material in relation to their (developing) creative practice.

Participants were recruited through purposeful sampling, targeting individuals who met the criteria of being currently enrolled in or having recently completed a game art programme and being actively engaged in visual creative practice. Individuals with a formal education in art history, or individuals with a design or programming specialisation within game education, fell outside the scope of this research, which focused on visual art practitioners. Access to these participants was provided through personal and professional networks of the researcher. Snowball sampling was employed where necessary to gather enough participants to achieve sufficient analytical depth.

The target sample size was approximately eight to twelve participants. This number was informed by the fact that in qualitative research, sample size is guided by the principle of informational adequacy rather than statistical representativeness (Braun & Clarke, 2021; Malterud et al., 2016). According to these scholars, larger samples do not inherently produce richer or more valid findings. Rather, depth of engagement with each participant and the analytical attention given to their responses determine quality. Prioritising depth of engagement over breadth of sampling was also realistic within the timeframe of a one-year master's programme.

3.4 DATA COLLECTION

3.4.1 Image Selection

3.4.1.1 Researcher-Selected Images

The study used four to six post-impressionist paintings as visual stimuli. This number aimed to balance sufficient variety against practical constraints of interview duration and participant attention. These images were selected to represent purposeful variety within the post-impressionist movement rather than narrowing to a single technique or artist. This approach allowed participants' selective attention to become meaningful data: what they noticed and emphasised across diverse works revealed what resonated with their visual frameworks. This

selection therefore represented a purposeful sample of the movement's range rather than an exhaustive survey.

Images were selected based on several criteria. Each work needed to be situated within the post-impressionist period (approximately 1880s–1910s) and represent a different artist or approach within the movement, ensuring visual variety across the selection. Chosen artworks needed to come from artists frequently associated with post-impressionism to support their established relevance and position within the art movement. Each image also needed to be available in high-quality digital reproduction and part of the public domain.

The final selection included the artworks listed in Table 3.1 below (full-resolution reproductions and source links are provided in Appendix A). The artworks were presented to participants in a fixed order across all interviews to support comparability. This order followed that of Table 3.1 and alternated between figurative and still-life or landscape subjects to avoid clustering similar compositions.

Figure 3.1 - *Bathers*, by P. Cézanne, Oil on Canvas, 1874-75, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Figure 3.2 - *Circus Sideshow (Parade de cirque)*, by G. Seurat, Oil on Canvas, ca. 1887, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Figure 3.3 - *Oleanders*, by V. van Gogh, Oil on Canvas, 1888, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Figure 3.4 - *The Repast of the Lion*, by H. Rousseau, Oil on Canvas, ca. 1907, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Figure 3.5 - *Steamboats in the Port of Rouen*, by C. Pissarro, Oil on Canvas, 1896, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Figure 3.6 - *Still Life with Teapot and Fruit*, by P. Gauguin, Oil on Canvas, 1896, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

Table 1.1 - Researcher-selected visuals

3.4.1.2 Participant-Selected Images

Prior to the interview, participants received a briefing asking them to select two artworks. One artwork of their choice that had influenced their thinking or practice as a game artist, and one traditional artwork, specifically a painting, that held meaning for them. The full briefing (plus consent form) document can be found in Appendix B.

Asking participants to select their own images shifted some agency to them and opened the interview with familiar works, easing into the later discussion of unfamiliar material. The open briefing for the first image aimed to avoid steering participants towards art historical sources, instead connecting the selection to their own creative practice. The second image narrowed the scope towards a meaningful traditional artwork, though participants retained agency in choosing which specific work fit the description for them. This more directed choice served several purposes: it established a baseline for discussing traditional art prior to the researcher-selected images and revealed possible patterns in participants' existing engagement with traditional art, such as whether they gravitated towards famous works, particular art movements, or styles.

3.4.2 Tools and Technology

The interviews were conducted remotely via the video conferencing software Microsoft Teams. Any platform offering screensharing, recording and automated transcription would serve as an adequate replacement.

The interviews were recorded with both video and audio, with participant consent obtained through a consent form built from the BUAs-provided template. Video recording served as a backup, allowing for review of non-verbal responses during image viewing where audio or transcript alone proved unclear. Recordings were stored securely on BUAs servers.

Researcher-selected images were displayed via screen sharing during the interview and shared with participants as a digital file beforehand. This sharing in advance was introduced following a pilot interview (the pilot summary and any resulting adjustments are documented in

Appendix C) and allowed participants to view high-resolution versions and adjust display settings such as zoom. Similarly, participants were asked to share their two selected images ahead of the interview so that either party could display them during the interview. All shared images were stored securely for reference during analysis.

During the interview, participants were invited to sketch or make visual notes using their preferred tools (paper or digital drawing software). Digital visual notes could be captured via screen share, and paper notes could be photographed and shared after the interview. No participants chose to create visual materials, but the option was offered consistently across all interviews and is documented here as part of the methodological design.

Interview recordings were transcribed using Teams' built-in transcription tool. All automated transcriptions were reviewed against the audio recording and corrected for accuracy before further analysis.

Coding and further thematic analysis steps were planned to be conducted using the qualitative data analysis software MAXQDA. MAXQDA supports systematic coding and theme organisation required for Reflexive Thematic Analysis and could be replaced by any tool with comparable functionality. (The analysis ultimately relied primarily on repeated listening to the audio recordings and note-taking; this deviation and its rationale are documented in Chapter 4.2)

3.5 INTERVIEW PROTOCOL

Each interview lasted approximately 60 to 90 minutes and was conducted in either Dutch or English based on the participant's preference. The semi-structured format follows established frameworks for qualitative interviewing (Kallio et al., 2016), balancing consistency across interviews through core questions while allowing flexibility to follow participant responses and probe emerging topics. The interview protocol used Feldman's (1994) four-stage critical method (Description, Analysis, Interpretation, Judgment) as a guide for structuring the stages. This approach was designed so that the interview would follow a meaningful progression from observation through interpretation to evaluative response.

Figure 3.7 - Visualisation of five stage interview protocol structure

3.5.1 Interview Structure

Each interview followed a five-stage structure, with each stage serving a distinct purpose. These stages are visualised in the figure 3.7 above. Observations relevant to the research question often emerged across multiple stages rather than being confined to a single stage of the

interview; recurring observations were pieced together across the stages. The full interview question guide is provided in Appendix D.

Stage 1: Opening (approximately 5-10 minutes)

The opening stage established rapport, explained the study, and gathered background information. After confirming consent and explaining the interview process, participants were asked brief background questions about their game art training, current practice, and any prior exposure to art history or traditional paintings. These questions focused on establishing the prior experiences and perspectives participants brought to the encounter. This stage aimed to provide the contextual information needed to interpret each participant's later engagement with the post-impressionist material.

Stage 2: Participant selected Image Viewing (approximately 15-25 minutes)

Participants presented and discussed the two artworks they selected prior to the interview. This discussion explored what drew them to these works, how the works had influenced their practice, and what meaning they made from them. This stage revealed participants' existing visual references and provided a baseline before introducing post-impressionist images. It also yielded preliminary findings that helped contextualise their responses to the researcher-selected images and served as an icebreaker by inviting participants to discuss familiar visuals. This stage intended to capture the language participants naturally used when discussing works they valued, functioning as a reference point against possible shifts in vocabulary or perception during Stage 3.

Stage 3: Researcher selected Image Viewing (approximately 35-45 minutes)

This stage formed the core of data collection. For each of the researcher-selected post-impressionist images, participants were invited to look, describe what they noticed, and what sense they made of the work. Where responses were superficial or brief, the researcher probed to encourage elaboration. After initial observation and interpretation, brief contextual information was provided (artist, title, date and a short contextual note), and participants were asked whether and how this information affected their perception or understanding. The stage concluded with questions about their overall response to the artwork. This stage was repeated for each of the selected visuals. The semi-structured approach allowed the researcher to follow participant responses, vary questions to avoid repetition, and probe more deeply when rich material emerged. This stage aimed to capture participants' perceptions, interpretations, and responses to post-impressionist works both before and after receiving historical context.

Stage 4: Reflection (approximately 15-25 minutes)

After viewing all images, participants reflected on the encounter as a whole and its connection to their creative practice. Questions in this stage explored what stood out, which images resonated most, possible connections to their own practice, and whether they could imagine applying any ideas or techniques they had identified. These questions addressed the second part of the research question: how participants relate the encounter to their own creative process and design outcomes. This stage sought to invite participants to articulate connections between the encounter and their own creative thinking, surfacing potential influences that might not be visible in responses to individual artworks alone.

Stage 5: Closing (approximately 5 minutes)

The interview concluded with an opportunity for participants to add anything not yet covered, ask questions about the study, and reconfirm their consent for the recording and collected data to be used in analysis. Participants were thanked and offered the opportunity to receive a summary of the findings once the study was completed.

3.5.2 Image Viewing Protocol

Each researcher-selected image was presented following a consistent protocol to support comparability across participants. Every image was displayed full-screen, with the researcher confirming visibility at the start of viewing. Each image was first displayed for approximately 30 to 60 seconds before any questions were asked, providing time for unguided observation. Participants were then invited to share their initial response without direction, prompted by open questions such as “What do you notice?” or “What sense do you make of this work?”

Following this unprompted response, probes addressed specific aspects as needed. Depending on participant focus, these follow-up questions prompted either for formal elements (colour, composition, technique) or for interpretive dimensions (meaning, emotion, narrative). After this initial period of viewing, interpreting and discussing, contextual information was provided: artist name, artwork title, date of creation, and a brief note of typically two to three sentences covering the artist’s background and historical circumstances. These contextual notes were prepared in advance, drawing primarily on The Metropolitan Museum of Art’s online collection entries. The notes were kept short to anchor the work historically without overloading the participant with biographical detail. All contextual notes can be found in the Appendix E. Participants were then asked whether and how this information affected their perception or understanding.

The image order remained consistent across all interviews to enable cross-participant comparison. Participants were informed in advance that the researcher-selected images would be paintings and that art history would be discussed as part of the study, but any further context, dates and artists were not introduced until the contextual notes were given for each image. This was a deliberate choice intended to avoid priming participants.

3.6 DATA ANALYSIS

Interview transcripts were analysed using Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) as developed by Braun and Clarke (2019, 2021). RTA involves identifying, analysing, and reporting patterns of meaning across qualitative data through systematic coding and theme development. It was selected because it is well-established and widely cited, showing its methodological credibility specifically for qualitative research.

The ‘reflexive’ element that distinguishes RTA from Thematic Analysis (TA) is that RTA consciously treats the researcher’s interpretive position as an active and acknowledged part of the analytical process, rather than a source of contamination to be eliminated (Braun & Clarke, 2019). For this study, where meaning-making and personal experience played a large role, the researcher interpretation inevitably shaped how the data was read and presented.

3.6.1 Analytical Framework

Four analytical dimensions (the broad areas of analytical interest) were developed prior to data collection as a sensitising framework, drawing on the conceptualisation of art historical literacy from Chapter 2 and the structure of the research question. They were intended to orient analytical attention, helping the researcher recognise patterns relevant to the research question, rather than to function as a fixed, pre-existing coding scheme (a predetermined list of codes applied uniformly to the data). In this study, coding proceeded inductively: codes were generated from the data itself rather than from a prior list, and the dimensions were used as a guide to how those codes could be organised and interpreted. Each dimension is expressed below as a set of guiding questions that framed the analysis; these questions helped focus what to attend to in the data without predetermining what would be found, so that observations falling outside the framework still received analytical attention.

Perception: How did participants describe what they saw? What visual elements did they notice? What formal language did they use to articulate visual qualities? (derived from visual literacy)

Contextualisation: How did contextual information (artist, title, period) affect participants' understanding? Did they situate artworks historically on their own, and if so, how? (derived from historical literacy)

Interpretation: How did participants make meaning from artistic choices? Did they engage with why artists made certain decisions? Did they connect techniques to broader artistic ideas or movements? (derived from aesthetic literacy)

Resonance: What connections did participants draw between the artworks and their own practice, visual references, or creative processes? Was there anything they might take forwards? If and how did they see such encounters fitting into their creative development?

Together, these four dimensions spanned both parts of the research question: perception, contextualisation, and interpretation addressed how participants perceived and made meaning from post-impressionist visual techniques and historical context, while resonance addressed how they related the encounter to their own creative process and design outcomes.

3.6.2 Analysis Process

Reflexive Thematic Analysis

Figure 3.8 - Visualisation of the iterative six phases of RTA (Braun & Clarke) within this study

The analysis followed Braun and Clarke’s (2006) six-phase process. The figure 3.8 shown above is a visual overview of those six phases. Reflexive Thematic Analysis treats these phases as iterative rather than strictly linear: codes and themes are revisited and refined as engagement with the data deepens, in line with Braun and Clarke’s (2019, 2021) framing of analysis as a generative practice rather than a fixed procedural sequence.

Phase 1: Familiarisation. Repeated engagement with the data through listening, reading, and note-taking, both during the interviews themselves and afterwards with the audio files and transcripts. Through this the researcher familiarised themselves with all of the gathered data.

Phase 2: Systematic coding. Coding, done inductively in this study, involved identifying segments of data (in the transcript or audio) that the researcher considered relevant and attaching a short descriptive label, a code being a concise label that captures something meaningful about a segment of data, to each. For example, a participant statement reflecting self-evaluative judgment might be coded “judges themselves”. When the same or a closely related code appeared repeatedly across the dataset, it began to form a pattern (a recurrence of the same or similar codes within or across transcripts).

Phase 3: Generating initial themes. Through the clustering of codes into patterns, and the clustering of patterns into broader groupings, initial themes were generated. A theme, as per Braun and Clarke, is the higher-level interpretive construct that integrates multiple codes and patterns into a broader claim about the data, rather than simply a frequently occurring topic. These themes were groupings of findings that the researcher interpreted as related or analytically significant across the dataset.

Phase 4: Reviewing themes. The initial (or preliminary) themes were checked against the dataset to ensure they accurately represented the data they claimed to capture. At this stage themes could be merged, split or discarded based on whether they cohered with the evidence. Themes were also discussed with peers and lecturers at this stage to surface alternative readings and challenge interpretations.

Phase 5: Defining and naming themes. Themes that survived the review phase were specified concretely in terms of what they captured, what data supported them, and how they related

back to the research question. The final themes were intended to encompass the most important findings of the study, with names chosen to communicate the analytical focus of each theme clearly.

Phase 6: Writing up the analysis. The analysis was written as a coherent narrative connecting data, interpretation, and discussion. Results were presented theme by theme to help the reader understand both the overarching theme and any subthemes it contained; interpretive claims were supported with participant quotes throughout.

Phase 6 was realised in the Findings and Discussion chapter, where themes, supporting data, and interpretive implications were presented at length.

3.7 ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS AND POSITIONALITY

3.7.1 Ethical considerations

Participants received a consent form in advance of their interview, explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and their rights. Participants were informed that they may withdraw at any point without needing to provide a reason, and that any data collected would be removed upon request.

To protect participant privacy, all data was anonymised. Participants' names, ages, and gender were not collected during this study. Pseudonyms were used when presenting quotes, and any identifying details that emerged during interviews were anonymised or removed. Where contextual detail about participants' backgrounds is reported (Chapter 4.2), it was kept at a level intended to situate responses without enabling identification.

Interview recordings and transcripts were stored on BUas servers, with access limited to the researcher and supervisors. The participants were informed of this in advance and gave consent to this through the given consent form.

Regarding the participant-selected images, participants consented to the use of their selections within the analysis; this could not, however, extend to publication of the images themselves. Where participants selected existing artworks, full provenance could not be confirmed in every case. Reproduction was therefore avoided, both to respect copyright and because these images functioned as context for participants' reflections rather than as primary data requiring visual presentation.

Interviews about personal perceptions may be subject to social desirability bias. To mitigate this, participants were informed and reminded throughout the interview that there were no right or wrong answers, open-ended questions were used so that participants were not led toward particular responses, and the opening stage aimed to build rapport before core questions. Despite these measures, some degree of bias will remain, and this is acknowledged.

Although the subject matter presents minimal risk, participant wellbeing remained a consideration. Some post-impressionist works in the selection depict nudity (notably Cézanne's *Bathers*), and all artworks originated from a specific Western European cultural context of the late nineteenth century. Participants were informed in advance about the general nature of the images and reminded that they could skip any image, skip any question, or end the interview at any time.

3.7.2 Researcher Positionality and reflexivity

The researcher's position as a game art practitioner with a personal interest in art history's relevance to the field shapes this study in ways that required reflexive attention (Berger, 2015). The personal interest originated in the researcher's own game art bachelor's programme, in which art history was noticeably absent, which was the observation that motivated this thesis (see Introduction). The insider perspective offered advantages, such as familiarity with game art practice, shared vocabulary with participants, and the ability to recognise discipline-specific nuances. It also invited risks, however, including confirmation bias towards findings that support art history's value and assumptions about what participants mean based on the shared background.

Several strategies aimed to address these risks. Interview questions were designed to be open-ended, avoiding steering language or framing that presupposed art history's relevance. During analysis, attention was given to data that contradicted or complicated the research hypothesis, not only data that supported it. Peer debriefing with lecturers and classmates provided external perspective on emerging interpretations, helping to identify where the researcher's assumptions might be shaping the analysis (Berger, 2015).

A specific risk worth naming concerns the contextual information provided during Stage 3. The contextual notes were drawn from established sources and limited to factual historical context, deliberately avoiding any personal judgement or evaluation. Even so, introducing this context possibly shaped what participants subsequently noticed and discussed. The protocol mitigated this by gathering participants' uninfluenced responses before any context was provided, yet the risk that even neutral framing led participants toward particular readings is acknowledged as part of the researcher's influence on the encounter.

Reflexive practice does not eliminate researcher influence but aims to make it visible and accountable (Braun & Clarke, 2019). Rather than claiming full objectivity, this study acknowledges the perspective of the researcher as part of the analytical lens. The researcher's interest in art history's potential value is transparent, and readers should evaluate the findings with this context in mind. This transparency, combined with the strategies outlined above, aimed to keep the analysis grounded in participant data rather than researcher assumptions.

4 FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 INTRODUCTION TO THE CHAPTER

This chapter presents and discusses the findings of the Reflexive Thematic Analysis (RTA) of fifteen interviews (eleven primary and four follow-ups) conducted with eleven game art students or recent alumni. Findings were interpreted in dialogue with the literature reviewed in Chapter 2. Each thematic section presents what participants said, draws on direct quotations to illustrate the patterns observed, and works through what those patterns might mean, both in the context of existing research and through the researcher's interpretation.

The chapter is structured around three themes developed through the RTA described in Chapter 3: Identity, Engagement, and Practical Application. These themes are presented in this order to follow the structure of the research question, which asks first how participants perceive and make meaning from the encounter (addressed in Themes 1 and 2) and second how they relate it to their creative process and design outcomes (addressed in Theme 3). The chapter opens with the changes that came up during data collection, presents a brief participant overview, and proceeds through the three themes in turn, followed by a section identifying patterns running across themes, before discussing the study's limitations. Recommendations, pedagogical implications, and the consolidated answer to the research question appear in the Conclusion chapter.

4.2 DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS PROCESS

This section describes how the interviews were conducted, where the procedure deviated from the methodology described in Chapter 3, and how the analysis proceeded.

4.2.1 Interview process

The main study comprised eleven primary interviews and four follow-up re-interviews, conducted between February and March 2026. Primary interviews followed the five-stage structure outlined in Chapter 3 and lasted between sixty and one hundred minutes, with several outliers extending to approximately one hundred and forty minutes. Re-interviews ran shorter and focused on the themes that had begun to emerge from the initial analysis; they were conducted with participants 1, 2, 4, and 5. Quotations drawn from a re-interview are marked with a '.2' suffix throughout this chapter (for example, P5.2), to distinguish them from the participant's primary interview (P5). (Both interview guides are provided in Appendix D).

Three aspects of the final procedure deviated from what was originally outlined in the methodology chapter.

First, although four to six researcher-selected images were planned, time constraints during interviews meant that most sessions used three post-impressionist works: *Bathers* by Cézanne (1874), *Circus Sideshow* by Seurat (1887), and *Oleanders* by van Gogh (1888). The method of viewing, analysing and discussing them did not change. Using fewer images than planned reduced the variety of visual stimuli, which may have limited the range of responses. However, it also allowed more sustained engagement with each work, prioritising depth over breadth. The three images still represented distinct artists, techniques, and subject matter within post-impressionism.

Second, the re-interviews were not part of the original research design. They were added after initial patterns from the first round of interviews surfaced areas the researcher identified as warranting deeper exploration. As Braun and Clarke (2019) describe, thematic analysis is a recursive rather than linear process, in which later stages can reshape decisions made at earlier ones, and later data collection informed by emerging patterns is consistent with this approach. The re-interviews enabled targeted follow-up on themes that the initial interviews had surfaced but not fully explored, yielding richer data on identity and attitudes towards art.

Third, the analysis was conducted primarily through repeated listening to audio recordings rather than through MAXQDA as originally planned. Working directly with audio recordings rather than relying solely on transcripts is a recognised approach in qualitative research. Halcomb and Davidson (2006) argue that verbatim transcription is not always necessary for rigorous qualitative analysis, and that researchers can engage meaningfully with audio data as a primary source without compromising analytical quality.

Choosing the audio listening approach was more responsive to the nuances of participant tone, hesitation, and emphasis than working from text alone, and these elements carried analytical significance in a study investigating perception and meaning-making. The trade-off was that MAXQDA would have provided more visible documentation of the coding process, which is an acknowledged transparency loss and further discussed as a limitation in Section 4.5.

Interview recordings were transcribed using Teams' built-in transcription tool and subsequently cleaned using Claude (under BUAs contract). The cleaned transcripts were retained as a secondary reference for locating specific passages and supporting the writing-up phase and remain available for review by other researchers upon request.

4.2.2 Analytical process

The analysis followed the six-phase RTA process described in detail in Section 3.6. Because the analysis proceeded as planned, the analysis phases will not be re-described in full here. What follows is a short summary of how that process played out in practice.

Familiarisation began during the interviews themselves, as the researcher conducted and recorded every session personally and noted initial impressions during and after each one, then continued through repeated listening to the recordings.

Coding proceeded inductively, with labels generated directly from participant language and the specific features of their responses; examples include "position towards art," "discomfort," "disinterest," and "possible practical application." The analytical dimensions set out in the methodology chapter (Perception, Contextualisation, Interpretation, and Resonance) oriented attention during this phase without functioning as a fixed coding scheme.

Generating initial themes involved clustering these codes into patterns and the patterns into broader groupings; it was here that Identity, Engagement, and Practical Application first took shape, distinct from the four dimensions even where they covered related conceptual ground.

Reviewing and defining and naming the themes then proceeded together and iteratively rather than as discrete steps: preliminary groupings were checked back against the recordings and transcripts, key passages re-listened to, and patterns compared across participants until the clustering stabilised, with peers and lecturers consulted to test alternative readings.

Writing up is the present chapter (Findings and Discussion). The process was markedly recursive: the Identity theme emerged only after the first interviews and fed back into later data collection and the re-interviews, so most of the phases were revisited rather than completed once.

Several strategies aimed to support the trustworthiness of the analysis. Negative cases (participants whose responses contradicted emerging patterns or who did not find the encounter relevant) were documented and included in the analysis rather than set aside. The researcher's positionality as a game art practitioner with a personal interest in the relevance of art history to the field was acknowledged in the methodology chapter (Section 3.7.2) and was taken into account during interpretation. And, as stated before, interpretations were checked repeatedly against the source recordings, notes and transcripts throughout the analysis. Aiming to confirm interpretations did not stray too far from what the participants expressed.

4.2.3 Participant overview

Before turning to the themes, a brief overview of the participant group situates the rest of the chapter. The intention here is descriptive rather than interpretive: the patterns discussed later are easier to read with a sense of who the participants were and what they brought to the encounter. Possible implications of specific background factors are taken up alongside the themes they affected.

The participant pool consisted of eleven game art students and recent alumni. Four participants contributed to both the primary and re-interview rounds. All participants were recruited through the researcher's professional and personal networks and were drawn predominantly from the HKU (Utrecht University of the Arts).

While participants shared a common educational context in game art, they arrived at this field through varied routes. Prior educational backgrounds included MBO-level programmes in game development, media design, and graphic design, as well as studies in cooking, robotics, architecture, social work, and history. One participant had completed pre-education programmes at an art academy and a film academy before entering game art. This diversity of entry paths meant the group, while united by their current or recent engagement with game art, did not share a uniform creative or educational foundation.

Within game art, participants' disciplinary focuses also varied, including stylised 3D environments and props, character art and 3D sculpting, 3D animation, concept art and creature design, narrative design, and UI design. Several participants described themselves as generalists rather than claiming a single specialisation.

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Participant	Status at time of interview	Prior education before HKU	Specialisation	Prior art engagement	Re-interview
P1	Recent alumni	MBO Game Development	Character art, 3D sculpting	Minimal (creative family, but limited personal engagement with art history)	Yes
P2	Recent alumni	Robotics	3D (general)	Minimal	Yes
P3	Recent alumni	Gap year, multiple applications	Generalist, aspiring art director	Active personal engagement (lifelong artist identity, Czech heritage connection to Mucha, personal art practice, secondary school art education)	Asked, No
P4	Student	MBO Media Design	Concept art, creature design	Minimal (self-rated knowledge as very low, negative school associations)	Yes
P5	Recent alumni	Directly from High school	2D-focused	Minimal (some museum visits through school and with parents)	Yes
P6	Recent alumni	MBO Cook, MBO Game Art	Stylised 3D environments and props	Minimal	Asked, No
P7	Recent alumni	HBO History	3D environments	Some personal engagement (sister is photographer/artist, history background, personal interest in older art)	Asked, No
P8	Student	HBO Social worker, graphic design	3D animation	Some personal engagement (graphic design background, interest in painterly styles)	Asked, No
P9	Recent alumni	MBO Media Design	Allround designer, narrative design	Minimal	No
P10	Recent alumni	HBO Architecture, engineering	Generalist (environments, game direction)	Some personal engagement (architecture background, used art movements in a game project)	No
P11	Student	Pre-education art academy, film academy	Art lead, generalist	Some personal engagement (father introduced art, emotional connection to traditional paintings)	No

Table 2.1 - Participant overview

Participants' prior relationships with art and art history varied notably, as reflected in the table above. This variation emerged during the opening stage of each interview through open-ended questions about background, education, and engagement with art. The categories in the table are the researcher's interpretations of what participants shared during those conversational responses rather than fixed-category self-assessments, and they are intended as a reference tool for situating individual quotations in this chapter within the broader sample.

At one end of this range, participants described an early or ongoing personal connection to art. One recalled visiting multiple museums with their mother, another described learning to look at art alongside their father, and a third spoke about their sister, a photographer, as having fundamentally shaped how they see the world: *"My sister is an artist. She's a photographer, but really the artistic side, not necessarily of people. I think that's had a really big influence on me, because she's ten years older than me, in a way she's always been a bit of a mother figure. I just notice that a lot of the ways I look at the world, I've maybe taken over from her a bit."* (P7).

At the other end, participants described art and art history as largely absent from their lives. P6, for example, described knowing *"not very much about art history"* and noted that traditional art was simply not something they engaged with outside of rare museum visits. The differences between these groups proved less pronounced than might be expected. Even participants with prior art engagement showed limited formal vocabulary, and participants without prior exposure demonstrated genuine perceptiveness when given time and structure to look. How this variation manifested across the three themes is discussed in each relevant theme section below.

It is of note that none of the participants reported receiving substantial formal art history education as part of their game art programme. Some participants described brief encounters such as a single lesson or a lecturer who encouraged museum visits, but none described art

history as a structured component of their curriculum. This was consistent with the patterns identified in the literature review (Section 2.1.2).

Participants were, as noted in the methodology chapter (Section 3.4.1), asked to bring two self-selected images for the second stage of the interview. These selections were treated as contextual rather than primary data, used to provide a better understanding of the existing visual frameworks participants brought to the encounter. For their first chosen visual, participants were asked to select a work that had influenced their thinking or practice as a game artist. The resulting selections were predominantly games and game-related concept art, a pattern picked up again in Theme 3's discussion of the narrow reference pools current practice draws on (Section 4.3.3.1). For their second chosen visual, selections clustered in several directions. Some participants chose surrealist works, aligning with a stated preference for fantasy and the unexpected. Others selected realistic environment paintings, connecting to interests in narrative and atmosphere. Two participants independently chose works from movements close to the one used in this study, one a Monet (impressionism, the precursor) and one a Van Gogh (post-impressionism itself) as their meaningful traditional artwork; both were among those with stronger prior art engagement.

4.3 THEMATIC FINDINGS

4.3.1 Theme 1: Identity

One of the most consistently recurring patterns across the interviews concerned how participants positioned themselves in relation to art, both as viewers of the post-impressionist works they encountered and as practitioners within game art. This theme was the least anticipated by the original analytical framework and emerged from the data after the first interviews. The strength and consistency with which identity-related material surfaced suggested that how participants perceived and made meaning from such an encounter might be shaped by who they understood themselves to be in relation to it.

A small terminological note before the first subsection: participants used the terms “*art*,” “*art history*,” and “*traditional art*” fluidly throughout the interviews. There appeared to be a felt distinction between ‘art’ as a broad concept and ‘traditional art’ as something more specific, typically referring to painting or pre-digital creative practice, but the boundaries were not consistently drawn. The quotations preserved participants’ own terminology as spoken throughout the chapter.

4.3.1.1 *Distance from the art world*

Several participants positioned themselves as outsiders to the art world, a stance that seemingly shaped how they approached the encounter from the beginning. Multiple participants expressed that art, particularly in its contemporary forms, could feel exclusive or inaccessible. Some referenced the Dutch notion of “*kunst met een grote K*” (art with a capital A) and described the world of fine art as carrying an air of pretension they found difficult to relate to or were even actively opposed to. One participant described art as “*zweverig*” (floaty, pretentious) and treated the art world as something to be sceptical of, positioned at a distance from their own creative practice.

When asked to reflect on this distance and what may have caused this feeling, some participants traced it to specific sources. P4.2 acknowledged that their initial response to traditional painting was shaped by what they called an unconscious negativity: *“With this kind of painting work, I come in more negatively, I think unconsciously.”*

Pressed on where this came from, they pointed to teachers at their MBO programme who were associated with the art world but who, in P4’s view, lacked practical competence and had not earned their authority. The lasting association was between traditional art and institutional pretension. P4 recalled a museum experience that captured this sense of distance: visiting and becoming frustrated at the collective admiration for what they perceived as a simple arrangement of coloured squares, asking *“Any toddler could do that for you. What’s so interesting about this?”*

P2.2 went further, calling art *“a destructive concept”* because of the internal contradiction they perceived: *“The frustration of it, people who all act like they know what it is, and at the same time want to say that nobody actually really knows what it is.”*

What is interesting about these responses, taken together, is that they describe how previous experiences with the art world appear to have shaped how some participants view art as a category. This was not a uniform pattern across the sample: some participants held this wariness more strongly and articulated it explicitly; others arrived closer to neutral curiosity. Every participant most likely brought some prior disposition to the encounter, but its intensity and clarity varied.

Where this wariness was present, it seemed to shape participants orientation towards art before any question about personal identification was even asked. The art world appeared as already alienating, already stamped as pretentious or inaccessible, and this coloured what came after. This starting orientation also carried forward: the identity work described in Section 4.3.1 happened against this background, and the honest uncertainty about art history’s relevance discussed further in Section 4.3.3 was, for some, a direct downstream effect. If the art world had felt unwelcoming, the question of whether to enter it through art history is asked from a guarded position. The interview context itself, however, did not seem to reproduce that wariness; even participants who articulated the strongest critical views engaged openly with the post-impressionist material and discussed it without visible defensiveness. The pattern is therefore best read as a starting orientation that previous experience appears to have laid down, not a fixed stance that resists new encounters.

This starting orientation mattered because it might have shaped how participants reacted when asked to position themselves in relation to fine art, including the specific move of partitioning game art and fine art into separate purposes, which is the focus of the next subsection.

4.3.1.2 The artist/maker partition

Related to this distance, a recurring distinction emerged between game art and fine art in terms of purpose. Game art was frequently described as inherently commercial and practical, made for a specific purpose or audience, while traditional art was associated with personal expression and emotion. P1.2 articulated this with particular clarity: *“For me, an artist is an individual who focuses a lot on the emotional level, whether that’s emotion from within themselves that they put into a work, or evoking emotion through their work, or simply wanting to give knowledge or insight about a specific subject. And a designer, that’s more in my eyes a practical field where the*

real action is: something really needs to be made. It has a specific goal that needs to be maintained, and emotion isn't always the point. Sometimes something simply needs to be there to be there."

This general sense of purpose difference seemed to align with how participants identified themselves within the art world. When asked directly whether they considered themselves artists, a question posed during the reflection-focused Stage 4, most participants responded with hesitation. P7 stated this most explicitly: *"I don't really see myself as an artist. I think that's maybe what I technically already am. But I feel that's a title I won't assign to myself, because the things I make just don't have that much impact. They don't really convey feeling. There's no deeper meaning. It's often just an image I enjoy making."* They then compared themselves to their sister, a photographer: *"She's really an artist, but I just don't see myself as an artist."* For P7, the artist label was bound to emotional depth, a criterion they expressed their own work did not meet, while simultaneously expressing a desire to change this: *"That's something I'd want to look into. Just how you can make game art so that it's more... that it's really art instead of support for gameplay."*

P10 offered another framing: *"I feel more like a maker than an artist. Because I just make things because I enjoy doing it. Not with the intention that it's art."* Asked whether others calling their work art would make them an artist, they replied: *"Apparently. If someone considers that art and I made it, then in their eyes I'm an artist. Then my own perception doesn't really matter anymore."* P10 placed the definition with the viewer rather than the maker.

P9 responded logically when asked whether they were an artist: *"Yes, I design things, so then yes."* But when asked whether they felt like one: *"No. Because 'artist' is so often seen as, at least I see it that way too, as a painter or something. Yeah, really that old traditional art."* For P9 the label apparently felt owned by traditional art in a way that excluded their digital practice by default.

This distinction was not limited to participants who identified primarily as designers. P3, who unlike most participants did describe themselves as an artist, nevertheless drew a clear line between their two creative modes: *"My persona as a game artist is kind of different from my artist persona, if that makes sense. Game art is more like commercial, and artist is something like what I do on my own."* This aligns, at the level of personal identity, with the purpose-based difference P1.2 described.

Despite the variation in reasoning, a common thread ran through these responses: participants held quite broad definitions of what art can be, often theorising openly during the interview about how far the category could be stretched (whether cooking is art, whether craftsmanship makes something art, whether the maker's intention or the viewer's reception defines it), while simultaneously declining to identify with the category themselves, even when their own broad definitions would, on the face of it, include them. This apparent contradiction is worth examining. The same participants who placed emotion in the domain of 'real' art also frequently described emotional resonance, narrative, and atmosphere as the qualities they most value in the game art they admire. P11, for example, stated elsewhere that *"the more emotion, the better I think it is."* The same quality, emotional resonance, thus appeared to be valued across both categories without participants treating its presence as a reason to dissolve the boundary between game art and fine art: the game art they admire can hold the qualities they associate with art, yet this does not, for these participants, change game art's category.

One reading of this contradiction is that participants are not distinguishing the content of emotion but the framing of purpose. Game art is understood as having a purpose external to

itself, commercial production, communicative function within a game, contribution to a larger product, while fine art is understood as having its purpose internal to itself: expression, exploration, the artist's own intention. Emotion can live in both contexts on this reading, but participants seem to treat the framing of purpose as the defining boundary. P1.2's wording supports this: the designer field is "where the real action is: something really needs to be made. It has a specific goal that needs to be maintained." The category boundary, on this reading, is drawn around purpose rather than around emotional content.

However, participants may be drawing the distinction between fine art and game art for reasons the interview format did not surface. What can be said based on the data is that the partition was something participants consciously drew themselves, and the identity work documented earlier in this theme is a possible source of it. P3's articulation of two personas is a particularly clear instance: rather than treating game art and fine art as one continuous creative identity, P3 partitioned practice across domains, holding a 'game artist' self and an 'artist' self as deliberately separate. This was consistent with the constructivist account of meaning-making developed in Chapter 2 (Section 2.3.4). Kegan, as summarised by Ignelzi (2000), argues that meaning is not transferred from event to individual but constructed between them, formed through the prior frameworks and experiences the individual brings to the encounter.

If meaning is constructed from what the individual brings, then the resulting artist/maker partition might be an artefact of the starting frameworks of the participants within this study.

What this section has shown is some of the prior framing in this sample: a wariness of the art-world category in some participants, a purpose-based partition between game art and fine art, and a tendency to hold broad definitions of art while declining to occupy the category personally. This artist/maker distinction both helps explain and nuances later findings; it offered a glimpse into how participants engaged with art historical material while also foregrounding the individuality of those responses in a way that complicates generalisation.

4.3.1.3 Felt consequences of art history's absence

Alongside the partitioning described above, several participants seemed to express self-judgement about their art-related knowledge, an observation that reoccurred throughout the interviews.

P1.2 described feeling ashamed going into the interview: *"A bit ashamed, because you know, we're going to talk about major works and I, even with an art academy background, can't always name them. I just think: oh, I should really just know this."* A related form of self-judgement appeared during Stage 2, when P3 hesitated about their selection of a traditional artwork. Despite choosing a deeply personal work, by an artist whose prints had hung in their childhood home, they reported initial doubt about putting it forward: *"At first I was thinking like, oh, maybe should I pick something else? Because I feel like Mucha is kind of a basic artwork to give."* Where P1.2 felt shame for not knowing enough, P3 felt shame for picking something 'too obvious'. Both responses seem to point to the same underlying anxiety about how their relationship with art, and the understanding around the subject, would be perceived.

An adjacent but more surface-level pattern was observed as well. Where the explicit self-judgement above involved participants articulating what they felt they should know, a quieter version of the same anxiety seemed to appear around the Van Gogh painting shown during Stage 3. Multiple participants appeared to recognise the work but hesitated to say so. P11

articulated this most directly when the artist was revealed: *"I knew it! Because he has those typical brushstrokes. But I thought: it looks so familiar. And I didn't want to say it."* P7 described the same hesitation: *"I wanted to say right away, is this Van Gogh, but I also didn't want to get it wrong by saying something completely incorrect."*

P4 traced this kind of anxiety, around getting the 'right' answer and being afraid to be 'wrong' while looking at artworks, to past educational experiences with art. During their reflection in Stage 4, they described expecting the researcher to correct them: *"I had actually expected it to be one of those cases where I'd be told: oh, but you're completely wrong, because that happens so often when you're looking at art history things in school. It's always: what do you see here? And you say: I see an apple. And then it turns out you're totally wrong, because the apple supposedly stands for something else entirely."*

Read interpretively, the gap in art history education might underlie the observed self-judgement in two related ways. The negative classroom experiences described in Section 4.3.1, evaluative framings in which engaging with art could be 'wrong', appeared to have shaped a wary disposition towards art-historical material that some participants carried into the present encounter. The second observation was that participants who had little exposure to art history described feeling ashamed, hesitant, or shy in discussing it precisely because they had had few opportunities to develop the vocabulary the subject seemed to expect. Some participants described the lack of art historical knowledge as a felt deficit; others, as the next subsection shows, did not. Either way, the absence of art history from their formal education appeared to shape how comfortably participants engaged with the material, and, as Theme 2 will show, also in the vocabulary they could bring to the act of looking. This connection between absence-in-education and capacity-to-engage is one the chapter returns to in Theme 3.

Taken together, these responses suggested that the structural absence Chapter 2 documented is also experienced by individual participants. The introduction noted that, in casual conversation, fellow students and lecturers had reported a felt sense of having missed something. The literature review showed the absence as a curricular and disciplinary phenomenon: what programmes do not include, what fields do not engage. The pattern found in this data suggested that the absence is, as hypothesised, not only a curricular pattern but also consciously experienced by the participants in this study. What participants articulated as troubling was not only the missing knowledge itself but the experience of feeling expected to know things they did not know, and the anticipation of being judged for not knowing.

One way to make sense of this felt, rather than merely structural, absence is through the idea of a community of practice. The concept of legitimate peripheral participation (Lave & Wenger, 1991), developed further in Wenger's (1998) account of communities of practice describes the experience of someone who is partially within a community of practice, a group united by shared activity and criteria of competence, but who has not yet fully mastered its competencies. The framework was not part of the original literature review and is invoked here as a possible lens rather than a foundation. What it offered in the present analysis is a name for what these participants seem to be reporting: the experience of sitting at the intersection of two communities of practice (game art and fine art / art history) while having internalised one community's criteria of legitimate participation without feeling fully competent in the other. The identity work documented in Section 4.3.1.2 might be one way participants manage this dual position; the self-judgement documented here may be another.

However, some of the self-judgement described above may partly be an artefact of the interview itself. Being interviewed about art history might have positioned participants as evaluatees on a topic they did not feel expert in, which can produce shame-adjacent responses. It was emphasised to participants that the interview was not a knowledge test, and the variation in responses (several participants showed no such self-judgement) suggests the observed pattern holds meaning, but possible social-desirability bias should be taken into account.

4.3.1.4 Absence as relief: an unexpected freedom

The self-judgement described above was not, however, the only way the absence of art history was experienced. For one participant the same gap functioned in the opposite direction, not as a deficit to apologise for but as a freedom. P5.2's re-interview complicated the framing of absence as straightforwardly a felt deficit: *"I don't need to know that much about this, so I can just have my opinion about it. I think it's beautiful or I think it's really ugly, without having to justify it. At the same time, when it's something game-related, I sometimes feel: oh, I studied for this. I should be able to have a well-argued opinion about this."*

Where the shame and hesitation described above showed one possible affective burden of art history's absence, P5.2's observation showed the same absence functioning as some kind of relief. Not knowing seemed to free this participant from the professional expectations they carry within their own field. Because art-historical knowledge is, according to them, not something game artists are generally expected to have, P5.2 could experience the absence as something they were permitted to have rather than something they should remedy. The freedom this afforded might therefore partly be based on a recognition that the gap is consistent across the field rather than an individual shortfall.

P4's earlier-described expectation of being corrected in school art history is the inverse of this freedom. When art history was institutionally framed as an evaluative domain, something one could be wrong about in a graded setting, it produced shame; when it was informally encountered without that evaluative framing, it could instead permit the kind of unargued opinion P5.2 describes. The same absence, in other words, could be experienced as a deficit or a freedom depending partly on whether the surrounding frame is evaluative.

This observation does not generalise from one participant to a broader claim, but it suggests something worth considering: the affective consequences of an encounter with art history are not predetermined by the encounter itself. They might depend on how the encounter is framed, and that framing could either reproduce evaluative pressure or suspend it. Variation in prior art engagement may also matter here; P5.2's freedom was partly enabled by their lack of professional investment in art, since they have no expertise to be evaluated against. Participants with more developed art engagement might not experience this same freedom. The relationship between prior art engagement and the affective experience of an encounter is developed further in Theme 3.

Despite the wariness and self-judgement documented above, participants engaged openly with the encounter itself, expressing curiosity and, in many cases, enthusiasm for the kind of structured discussion the interview offered. This openness extended to a near-unanimous sense that art history has some place in game art curricula, which will be discussed further in Section 4.3.3.

The three observations developed across this theme; distance from the art world, the artist/maker partition, and the felt consequences of art history's absence alongside the unexpected freedom available within it, together suggested that participants navigate art history's absence not just as a knowledge gap but as a more complicated terrain of identity. That terrain shaped both how they understood themselves in relation to art and what they looked for when they looked at it. In doing so, this theme began to address the first half of the research question: who participants understood themselves to be in this encounter is part of how they perceived and made meaning from the post-impressionist material they viewed. The next theme moves to the act of looking itself.

4.3.2 Theme 2: Engagement

The previous theme examined how participants positioned themselves in relation to art. This theme attends to what they did when actually looking at the post-impressionist works: the criteria they brought to the act of looking, the vocabulary they reached for, and what extended engagement surfaced for them. Together, these address the first half of the research question more directly: how participants perceive and make meaning from post-impressionist visual techniques.

The theme opens with the criteria participants brought to the encounter, since these sat between identity and engagement: they reflected what training and prior experience had cultivated as standards of judgement, and they shaped what participants noticed. The remaining subsections turn to participant's available vocabulary, default modes of attention and the role of context, and finally to what sustained, guided looking surfaced. One feature of this theme worth flagging is that the observations here are inseparable from the research method. Prolonged looking, probing questions, and the structured provision of context were features of the visual elicitation approach, not conditions that arose naturally. What the data showed was what happened when participants were given a structured opportunity to look and reflect.

4.3.2.1 Evaluative orientations

This subsection examines how participants decide, often without conscious deliberation, whether an artwork warrants their attention. This question matters because it surfaces what participants bring to the encounter, the criteria they apply to deciding what is interesting, what holds attention, and what feels worth engaging with. Five orientations recurred across the interviews: innovation, curiosity, narrative, craftsmanship, and personal connection.

Innovation was central. Whether a work did something unexpected or distinctive, in composition, subject, or technique, appeared to affect how deeply participants engaged. Participants responded more positively to works they perceived as doing something they had not seen before, while works that felt conventional or redundant drew less sustained attention. P2 captured this orientation when reflecting on what holds their interest: *"I think in traditional art I'm mainly looking for unique things that when you look at them you suddenly think: oh yeah, that's also an interesting way to look at something."*

Closely related was curiosity. Works that raised questions or invited the viewer to wonder about the artist and the circumstances of creation tended to draw extended engagement. P11 demonstrated this while viewing Cézanne's *Bathers*: after the contextual information about Cézanne's documented discomfort with female models was provided, they speculated about the physical circumstances: *"I immediately look at the models, how they're drawn. It really looks as if he was just standing there in real life with his little painting. But that wasn't the case. So I wonder whether he made this in some depressive dark attic room, or whether he was actually outside."*

The presence or absence of a legible narrative also appeared to affect engagement depth. Participants described searching for a story within the image or its surrounding context, and works offering an intriguing narrative thread tended to hold attention longer. This is the same narrative-valuing as seen in Section 4.3.1.2, where participants named emotional resonance and story as what they admire in 'good' game art; the criterion they applied to their own field was thus also operative when they looked at unfamiliar traditional works.

The concept of *"ambacht"* (craftsmanship) recurred when participants described what they valued in artworks. This was expressed as respect for the time, skill, and physical effort visible

in an artwork. P7 described how a single brushwork line could create an immersive sense of atmosphere that made the painting feel almost like a moving image. Several participants extended this respect for craft to a specific interest in seeing works in person, noting that physical presence allows the viewer to perceive the artist's hand directly. P1.2 described this quality: *"I find the works made by the artist themselves more meaningful. It feels closer, as if I genuinely have a piece of that artist hanging in my room, rather than just their work."* That all works were viewed via screen share rather than in person bears on this particular criterion and is taken up again as a limitation in Section 4.5.

Finally, personal connection to an artwork was reported as something that increases engagement with it. P5.2 observed: *"I think that art I find beautiful and can really appreciate automatically gives me a bit more of a feeling that I'm closer to it, because then I'm automatically somewhat interested in it."* P11 described a similar dynamic with traditional art specifically, noting that recognising something familiar in a centuries-old painting creates an emotional connection to the artist, *"even though they've long been dead."* The same participant also described feeling more connected to the painter's humanity when a work showed visible human touch or felt imperfect rather than polished, a small but interesting extension of the craftsmanship criterion in which legible imperfection, rather than visible mastery, became the route to connection. P2.2 raised a related point: as a game artist, encountering a composition or technique that resembles something from their own practice prompts faster and deeper engagement.

What is interesting about these observations is what they seem to reveal about how design training shapes the way participants approach unfamiliar visual material. Lawson (2005) and Cross (2011) both argue that design education does not simply transfer technical skills but cultivates characteristic ways of attending to and evaluating visual work, ways that distinguish designers' judgements from those of non-designers and that are sustained by the professional community. The criteria identified here are recognisable as design-shaped. Innovation matters because design rewards distinctive solutions to recognisable problems. Narrative matters because narrative is a core organising principle in game development. Craftsmanship matters because visible craft is one of the things designers learn to recognise and value in each other's work. These criteria thus form a bridge between the participants' identity, examined in Theme 1, and how that identity shaped engagement.

4.3.2.2 When trained perception constrains

The criteria above, and the design-thinking lens that frames perception through them, had a particularly observable effect in one specific example. Several participants, in response to the Van Gogh painting, described feelings of unease triggered by visual elements that violated their expectations of spatial or perspectival logic. P11 described the scene as feeling like everything was about to slide off the table and even interpreted this as a deliberate criticism of the *"saai"* (boring) still-life genre. P7 noticed similar spatial irregularities: the left corner of the table stopping abruptly behind the book, the vase having *"quite a strange shape,"* and the books being stacked in an *"impossible"* way. Another participant mentioned that if a cat jumped on the table everything would fall off because it was all so close to the edges. The shared element across these responses is that the spatial distortions were experienced as feeling *"wrong"* first, and only after could be seen as expressive or stylistic. In game art, perspectival accuracy and spatial coherence are often (though not universally; some games deliberately play with these) treated

as functional requirements: players need to navigate spaces, judge distances, and read environments reliably.

When this trained expectation met post-impressionist works that deliberately subvert spatial conventions, the result for some participants was perceptual discomfort rather than aesthetic appreciation. As referenced before, Cross's (2011) point about characteristic design judgements becomes visible here: criteria cultivated through training do not simply enable seeing, they can also constrain it. Spatial accuracy may be one such criterion, and its violation was registered, for some participants in this study, as wrongness rather than as a possibility worth exploring. The observation rests on a specific work and a subset of participants, but it makes the broader analytical point concrete: the criteria participants bring to looking shape how they engage, in multiple observed directions.

4.3.2.3 Vocabulary and tacit knowledge

A noteworthy pattern across the interviews was the range of vocabulary participants used when describing the post-impressionist works, and the equally striking observation that vocabulary range did not seem to map neatly onto perceptiveness.

At one end, some participants demonstrated technical vocabulary drawn from their own practice. P8 consistently used terms like *“brushstrokes,” “toetsen”* (painterly marks), *“muddy colours,”* and *“contrast”* when describing the works. P6 used terms like *“compositie,” “value check,” “belichting”* (lighting), and even *“subsurface scattering,”* a developed jargon vocabulary that, notably, appeared most often when they were discussing their own work process rather than when describing the post-impressionist paintings themselves. Their descriptions of the post-impressionist works were comparatively more surface-level, even when game-art jargon appeared in them.

P3, who had engaged with art history through both personal interest and secondary education, demonstrated the most consistently art-historical vocabulary across their interview. They referenced *“complementary colours,” “plein air” painting, “shape language,”* and recognised the Venus pose in Cézanne's *Bathers*, being one of the few participants to make a direct art-historical reference of this kind. P3's descriptions were also notably more historically situated than most others in the sample. They spontaneously referenced specific art movements and connected stylistic choices to the historical conditions of their time (war, social conditions, the emotional content artists were responding to). This positioning of intention against historical context exemplified the historical literacy dimension defined in Chapter 2 (Section 2.3.2). Wineburg (2001) characterises historical literacy not as encyclopaedic knowledge of facts but as the skill of reasoning about the relationships between people, events, and circumstances in the past, a framing Nokes (2011) extends by emphasising that the underlying competence is the ability to read and reason with historical evidence rather than to recite it. P3's reading of the Cézanne and the Seurat in terms of the social and emotional conditions artists were responding to is recognisable as that kind of reasoning in action. The pattern stood out partly because few other participants discussed the works in this way.

At the other end, P9's descriptions of the same works were brief and concrete. Their first observation of Cézanne *Bathers* was simply: *“That ghostly thing standing behind that woman, I can see a little face in it.”* Their interpretation of the scene was equally direct: *“Nicely free. They're just naked in nature and nobody cares, because everyone is naked.”* When asked about their *“interpretation,”* P9 asked what the word meant. P9 did however produce a sharp formal observation about an unusual figure pose, describing a man (notably, the only participant to

read the figures as men) whose body position was something *“I don’t stand like every day”*. This was a clear observation about anatomy and posture expressed in everyday language rather than art-analytical terms.

This range suggests something about the relationship between vocabulary and perceptiveness. P9’s observation about the unusual pose was perceptive in substance even though it was not articulated in art-analytical vocabulary, which suggests that across the sample vocabulary functioned as a resource for articulation rather than as a measure of what participants were capable of seeing. This connects back to how visual literacy is defined in the literature. Serafini (2017), discussed in Section 2.3.1, frames visual literacy as “a process of generating meanings in transaction with multimodal ensembles” rather than as a set of formal decoding skills, and the ACRL standards similarly describe it as the ability to interpret, evaluate, and use visual media without requiring that this interpretation take art-historical form. On those framings, P9’s perceptive observation in everyday language and P3’s perceptive observation in formal vocabulary are different surface expressions of related meaning-making activity. Polanyi’s (1966) notion of tacit knowledge, the distinction between what people know and what they can say, names this gap: practitioners often know more than they can explicitly articulate, with significant knowledge operating below the level of formal language. Through this lens, P9’s perceptiveness was tacit; the absence of art-historical vocabulary did not signal an absence of seeing, only an absence of the formal language that would make the seeing more easily communicable. Schön’s (1983) account of knowing-in-action, discussed in the same section of chapter 2, extends this to design practice specifically, where competent judgements are made without the underlying reasoning being articulated.

This matters in two ways. First, it cautions against reading a participant’s lack of art-historical vocabulary as a lack of visual understanding; the seeing and the saying are not the same thing, and the participants in this sample could often see more than their vocabulary let them express. Second, it reframes what art history might offer game art students: not the capacity to see, which participants already demonstrated, but a shared language for naming, comparing, and discussing what they see.

A final related observation across the sample is worth recording here. Several participants demonstrated an understanding of what are typically called art principles, anatomy, colour theory, composition, lighting, in their own work and could recognise these elements in the post-impressionist paintings. What was notably absent for many of them, however, was the conscious connection back to art history as being the source. Anatomy and colour theory functioned for these participants as freestanding ‘art principles’ rather than as accumulated knowledge inherited from particular historical traditions and movements. This may explain part of the difficulty around discussing the post-impressionist works in art-historical terms. It is a small but interesting disconnect between practice and self-understanding worth flagging, and one that connects to the educational application discussion in Section 4.3.3.

4.3.2.4 Default modes and the role of context

Alongside vocabulary differences, participants showed distinct default modes of engagement, characteristic patterns of where attention went first. P6, P7, and P8 tended towards technique-first observations: brushstrokes, colour, composition, and spatial logic before anything else. P11 and P10 leaned towards emotional and narrative responses first. P9, P2, and P4 went directly to concrete content: who is depicted, what they are doing, what looks unusual. These defaults

remained relatively stable across the multiple artworks viewed within each interview, which suggests they reflect something more durable than a momentary response to one work.

Some participants became aware of their defaults during the interview. P1.2 caught themselves applying a practical lens to the artworks: *“There are so many elements that give the image so much more value, that actually get pushed to the side a bit, because I’m really looking at: OK, how can I go from this to that?”* They explicitly connected this to their training, noting that the emphasis on pipeline and practical execution meant their first instinct with any visual material was to assess how it could be translated into their own medium. P1.2’s self-awareness shows the default mode being recognised as a default rather than as the only way to see, and, once recognised, as something that could be set aside long enough to notice what it had been filtering out.

Beyond defaults, the provision of contextual information during Stage 3 itself shaped engagement, and did so variably. For some participants, it appeared to confirm or reframe what had been initially observed. P1.2 described how the structured progression, looking first and then receiving context, became generative over the course of the interview: *“I really started to notice more things and understand: oh wait, it’s not that they just randomly put something down. It’s the periods that people themselves go through and how they can translate that into their work.”* For other participants, context produced no detectable shift. A small but consistent observation across these latter cases is that many participants produced an audible response on hearing the context, a *“huh,”* an *“oh,”* a moment of registered surprise, but then articulated little or no change in how they read the work. The surprise and the perceptual shift appear, at least in this sample, to be somewhat mismatched: new information could be received and considered without then altering the prior reading. This is a tentative reading that would require designed follow-up to test more directly.

Read together, vocabulary, default modes, and the role of context appear to be aspects of the same underlying pattern. Each participant approached the looking task with a set of resources (vocabulary, default attention patterns) and a set of responses to new information (context that either deepened or did not deepen what they were seeing). Together these constitute what might be called an interpretive habit, the cluster of things a participant tends to do when they encounter visual material. These habits map closely onto what Lawson (2005) and Cross (2011) describe as the durable cognitive patterns design education cultivates, and onto the constructivist account of meaning-making developed in Section 2.4.2. Participants are not encountering the post-impressionist works as blank receivers but as practitioners whose prior training shapes what registers and what does not.

4.3.2.5 What sustained engagement surfaced

Beyond the immediate task of looking and describing, several participants reflected during Stage 4 on how the experience of sustained, guided engagement compared with their typical interactions with art. The most consistently reported observation across the sample was that prolonged looking, combined with open-ended dialogue, drew out responses participants did not initially expect to have.

P8 articulated this directly: *“The longer you think about it or are in conversation about it, the more things actually come up. Because when I go to museums, I often just look by myself and then everyone is quiet. So then it’s just your own thoughts, but I think by also getting questions, you start thinking more deeply about other things. So elements that you might not immediately come*

up with if you just look at it.” Others corroborated: P11 valued “That probing, I really liked that, because at first glance I don’t say that much, but when you really keep asking and keep looking, then it all comes up.”; P6 added a different dimension, describing how extended engagement with the Seurat led them to diverge from their initial reading rather than simply deepen it: “Especially with your second example, the circus, when I think about it for a long time, I started to deviate more from what the original idea was.”; and P5 noted the encounter made tangible “How interesting it can be to look at something for longer than two minutes, and that it can really add a lot.”

This parallels Visual Thinking Strategies (VTS) (Yenawine, 2013) which emphasises open questions (“What’s going on here?” “What do you see that makes you say that?”) and prolonged engagement. Housen’s (2002) research on aesthetic development found that structured, sustained looking supported by dialogue draws out perceptual and interpretive capacities that viewers did not previously display. The convergence is not coincidental, VTS informed the research design, but the modest contribution here is to extend that pattern to a specific population: game art students and recent alumni. Sustained and structured looking surfaced new responses even in participants whose training already exposes them to visual material regularly.

Beyond what surfaced during the looking itself, several participants reflected on whether the encounter had shifted anything more durably. Most reported no direct tangible change, a valid finding, but several described smaller shifts in intention or openness worth noting. P5.2 described becoming “*a bit more open*” to looking at art after the interview, suggesting they would approach museum visits differently. P11, who already had experience with art through their father, noted a concrete intention: “*I really liked that you could tell those stories afterwards, so that I could first look for myself. [...] In that way I do think: oh yeah, that sounds nice to do differently next time.*” P1.2’s response went further. In their re-interview, conducted several weeks after the original encounter, they described a tangible change: starting their workday by looking at art other than game art or ArtStation references, framing the encounter as having broadened their reference pool: “*The scope stayed quite narrow and it does feel as though that’s been widened a bit, which I can also take into my own work. [...] I can now also use it as a reference point, as a looking-back point, as inspiration for work.*”

The reported shifts, both in how participants viewed the work and in what they might take away from it, should be read carefully: they are participants’ self-reported perceptions, not independently verified behavioural changes. The shifts reported during the re-interviews should also be read with caution, since the re-interviews took place relatively shortly after the original encounter, so longer-term effects remain unassessed.

Participants who reported no such shift provide an important counterbalance. The encounter surfaced responses, openness, and intentions for some participants but not for others. As with the other themes, the data therefore supports a more conditional claim. Sustained, structured engagement can surface perceptual and interpretive responses, and might shift intention or openness for some participants, but does not do so uniformly. Section 4.4 discusses this conditional pattern overarching all three themes in more detail.

The three patterns developed across this theme, the criteria participants brought to looking, the relationship between vocabulary, default modes, and context, and what sustained engagement surfaced, together suggest that engagement with post-impressionist works was neither a

uniform skill participants either possessed or lacked nor a fixed, predetermined response. It unfolded under particular conditions, shaped by what participants brought (vocabulary, criteria, default modes) and by what the encounter offered (sustained time, context, probing dialogue). This addresses the first half of the research question by showing that perception and meaning-making in this encounter were active and conditional processes. The next theme moves to the second half of the question: whether and how this engagement connected to participants' own creative practice.

4.3.3 Theme 3: Practical Application

The previous two themes have examined how participants positioned themselves in relation to art and how they engaged with the post-impressionist works during the interviews. This theme addresses the second part of the research question: how participants relate the encounter to their creative process and design outcomes. It explores whether and how participants encountered post-impressionist material (and, by extension, art-historical material more broadly) as applicable to their own practice, the conditions under which application felt possible, and the spectrum of responses ranging from clear practical connection to honest disinterest.

One observation worth flagging at the start: the responses in this theme show more variation than those in the previous two. Where participants converged on patterns of identity and engagement, they diverged more noticeably on the question of practical application. Some saw clear and immediate connections; some saw possible connections that required additional conditions to feel real; some saw fundamental barriers; and some saw no relevance at all.

4.3.3.1 The narrowness of current reference pools

Before examining what participants might see as applicable, a baseline was established by discussing where they currently draw their creative inspiration. The pattern across the interviews was consistent and aligned with the field self-referentiality (the ‘echo chamber’) discussed in the introduction, developed in Chapter 2 and noted earlier this chapter: participants drew primary inspiration from within the game industry and adjacent digital fields.

During the opening stages of the interviews, concept art on ArtStation, other games, animated films, and occasionally photography were frequently cited inspiration sources. P6 described looking “*mainly for concept art on ArtStation, then I save it in a folder*” and confirmed these references were typically game-focused. P11 similarly described drawing from their two or three favourite games, or using a game UI database when those references did not fit a given brief. The reference pool was, in most cases, almost entirely within or adjacent to game production: either full-fledged games or concept art made for them.

Notably, several participants identified this reference pool as narrow themselves, often in vivid language and unprompted. P1.2 described the game art field as “*very blindfolded*”. P3 articulated the same observation more fully: “*What you see now is that the AAA gaming industry is kind of cannibalising on itself. It’s not drawing from new inspiration, they’re just drawing inspiration from each other. So you get the same thing every time.*” P3 went on to describe deliberately avoiding too many game art references in their own mood boards as a result. P6 described an art director they admired who deliberately looks at traditional art and real life rather than other game art: “*He also thinks that a lot of modern game art looks very similar to each other, he really stands out.*” The criterion P6 used to identify this director as worth admiring, namely the distinctiveness, doing something the rest of the field is not doing, aligns with the ‘innovation’ criterion documented in Section 4.3.2.1, but also argues for the relevance of including art historical material in game art practice. A practitioner who draws from outside the echo chamber, registers as innovative and admirable.

Some participants also noted that the industry context may itself constrain stylistic experimentation. P10 observed that indie games offer more room for creative exploration “*because people there have more creative freedom to experiment without ten million stakeholders thinking it’ll blow their budget.*” P7 noted that even minor stylistic deviations in AAA games can

provoke negative reactions: *“Even if you deviate just a little bit from the norm, people already...”*, trailing off but suggesting that commercial game production rewards conformity over experimentation.

That multiple participants independently identified this self-referential pattern is notable. Bourgonjon et al. (2017) and Murray (2020) both identified disciplinary self-referentiality at the scholarly level, where art history rarely engages with game studies and game studies rarely employs art historical methods. The study observed a possibly comparable pattern at both the industry and individual level, where game artists and game art students draw primarily from game art and adjacent digital fields. If this is the case, then these levels are unlikely to be independent as the industry influences the students training to enter said industry. Goldschmidt’s (2011) account of design fixation describes the difficulty designers have generating ideas outside an established reference set. It names a cognitive version of this dynamic and seems to align closely with what this study has referred to as the possibly problematic echo chamber; the repeated exposure to a narrow reference pool shrinks the space of options that feel available.

One final caveat: participants who articulated the narrowness most clearly were also among those with stronger prior art engagement or more developed self-direction. So the pattern may be most visible to those who have already partially escaped it. The observation is not that all participants experienced the field’s self-referentiality as a constraint, but that those positioned to notice it did, which meant the finding was shaped partly by who was able to recognize and articulate the constraint, and may not fully capture who experiences it.

4.3.3.2 Medium distance: barrier or puzzle

A consistent point of discussion across the interviews was the perceived distance between traditional painting and digital game art. Several participants returned to this distinction unprompted, and the same perceived distance functioned differently for different participants.

For some, the distance between media functioned as a clear barrier. When asked during Stage 4 whether anything from the post-impressionist works could be relevant to their practice, P9 plainly said that none of them were. They explained that their work has a particular style that does not match the three works shown: their own work is digital and reads as realistically drawn, in contrast to the abstraction and visible painterliness of these works. When asked whether the encounter had changed how they look at art, P9 was equally direct, saying this was how they had always looked at art and that nothing had changed. An interesting tension is worth noting: P9 elsewhere described having used traditional paintings as reference for material and anatomy studies. This might suggest that the medium-distance barrier is more situational than absolute, applying to whole-aesthetic transfer rather than to specific reference uses, though it may equally reflect how P9 interpreted the question.

For others, the same distance functioned as a creative puzzle. P10 described a recurring thought when viewing the paintings: *“I naturally always think: oh, how could you transfer this same texture digitally?”* The gap between media was acknowledged but treated as a translation challenge rather than as a reason for disengagement. P8 went further, describing active plans to incorporate painterly aesthetics into their current 3D project, exploring technical approaches to approximate a painterly feel in a digital medium.

The variation suggests something about how the distance between media functions. The distance was recognised by virtually all participants; what differed was what participants did

with it. For some, the distance was sufficient grounds to dismiss the source. For others, the distance was the very thing that made the source interesting, a translation challenge rather than a wall.

The “puzzle” orientation echoes the co-evolution model Dorst and Cross (2001) developed from protocol studies of industrial designers (Section 2.4.3), in which creative work emerges through continuous reframing between problem and solution spaces. P10’s recurring thought, “how could you transfer this same texture digitally?”, is recognisable as exactly that kind of reframing: the work is encountered not as a fixed source to be replicated but as a prompt that opens a question about translation. Participants who framed the distance as a puzzle were, possibly, doing something close to this co-evolutionary move, while the barrier-framing participants might have read the gap as a property of the source itself rather than as material for reframing.

This has a possible parallel in the knowledge transfer literature reviewed in Chapter 2. Barnett and Ceci’s (2002) taxonomy identifies multiple dimensions along which transfer between domains can be measured, including modality (the physical medium of expression) and functional context (the purpose the work serves). On several of these dimensions, the distance between post-impressionist painting and digital game art is substantial; their analysis suggests that transfer becomes more difficult as more dimensions diverge.

The variation observed in this study is consistent with this transfer framing in one respect (the dimensional gap is large and not all participants found ways across it) but complicates it in another. The size of the gap did not, on its own, predict whether transfer felt possible. Different practitioners constructed the same distance differently. The transfer literature seems to treat the gap between two domains as if it were a fixed property of the relationship between them, but in this data the gap looks less like a fixed property and more like material each practitioner works with differently. That work appears to be shaped by what Themes 1 and 2 have already documented. A participant’s identity work (do they treat game art and fine art as fundamentally different categories or as members of the same broad family?) and their evaluative criteria (does an unfamiliar work register as innovative or as broken?) seem to condition whether a medium-gap becomes a barrier or a translation challenge. Read this way, the transfer literature is most useful here in combination with the identity and engagement findings rather than on its own: the gap is real, but a participant’s response to it is partly shaped by how they have been trained to look and how they understand themselves in relation to what they are looking at.

The reading described above is more suggestive than what the data directly establishes. The transfer literature was developed primarily in educational and cognitive contexts, and applying it to creative practice is an extension. What the data supports is that the distance between media functioned as a variable rather than as a fixed property, and that the navigation itself appears connected to the identity work and looking-criteria documented earlier.

4.3.3.3 *Honest uncertainty*

Alongside the distance between media, several participants expressed more fundamental uncertainty about whether looking to art history was worthwhile at all. This read less as dismissiveness than as a genuine question, rooted in the observation that participants had developed their practice perfectly well, in their own estimation, without art-historical reference.

P9's response was the clearest case across the entire interview. Their disinterest in the post-impressionist works was not just a polite dismissal but a consistent, grounded position. The works did not match the style of their current work; the encounter had not changed how they looked at art; and they did not anticipate that it would in the future. P9's position was internally coherent, and the interview gave no evidence that it represented a misunderstanding of what was being shown or an inability to engage. P9 simply did not see relevance and said so.

P2 expressed disengagement in a different form. Asked whether the encounter had provided new inspiration, they responded: *"Maybe the right one, unconsciously? But so quickly, I can't really imagine it."* They explained that when inspiration strikes for them, it clicks immediately, and this encounter had not produced that click. Asked whether they would look at art differently after the interview, P2 responded simply: *"No, I don't think so."* Unlike P9's categorical disinterest, P2's response seemed more conditional: not that art historical material is irrelevant, but that a single brief encounter may not be sufficient to produce the kind of resonance that drives their creative process.

This set of responses was surprising to the researcher: that participants who had completed creative-arts education could find art history not just irrelevant in passing but irrelevant in general. However, these cases should not be read as failures of the encounter, or as outliers to be set aside. They are part of what the data shows. If the chapter's overall argument is that an art historical encounter can have value under certain conditions, the corresponding observation is that there are participants for whom those conditions appear not to apply, at least in the form this study examined.

4.3.3.4 Conditions for connections

Despite the reservations and uncertainties documented above, several participants did identify specific points of practical connection, sometimes as concrete plans, more often theorised possibilities. These connections help map how art-historical engagement might be practically applicable, where in their process participants thought it could enter, and what kind of engagement they thought would be most useful.

Connections clustered around particular visual qualities. Colour was mentioned most frequently. P8 described unexpected colour placement as what drew them to both Disco Elysium and traditional paintings: *"There are a lot of muddy colours, natural colours. But everywhere there are actually a lot of almost hidden little colours worked in, where you wouldn't expect them."* P6 noted: *"I also find the colour use of the shadow interesting, that purplish quality. That's also something I sometimes add in my stylised work, purple shadows."*

Painterly aesthetics and visible brushwork formed a second cluster. P8 explicitly connected traditional paint strokes to their current project: *"I think this kind of painterly style is really cool, so in my process it's still planned [...] I would absolutely love it if I could sometimes apply it."* They described considering technical approaches like normal maps to approximate a painterly feel in a 3D production. P5.2, when asked what they would look for in traditional paintings as inspiration, described a range including colour, textures, and atmosphere: *"The colours or the textures or something, see if you could use that, yeah, kind of weave the vibe of a painting into your visuals, see if you could get it to feel somewhat the same."* They added an important qualifier: the artwork would need to produce a strong emotional response before it would function as a primary inspiration source, connecting back to the personal-connection criterion identified in Section 4.3.3.1.

One participant had actually performed this kind of transfer in a real project. P10 described choosing expressionism as a visual direction for a game because it matched the fictional world's historical context: *"Basically looked at traditional painting: OK, which art movements were active in our non-fictional world at that time. And eventually that led to expressionism. And that was then used as inspiration for the game."* This is a concrete example of art historical knowledge informing a game art direction in practice, not just hypothetically. The visual style was used as inspiration, but the entry point into expressionism was historical context rather than aesthetic appeal alone. This example might support the case for teaching context besides technique, a point the educational discussion in Section 4.3.3.5 develops further. The industry cases documented in Section 2.1.3 (Cuphead's (Studio MDHR Entertainment Inc., 2017) use of 1930s Fleischer animation; Ōkami's (Clover Studio, 2006) Ukiyo-e and sumi-e; The Master's Pupil's (Pat Naoum, 2023) Monet) suggested that this kind of transfer is done at the field level; P10 gives a tangible example of an individual practitioner attempting the same transfer in their own creative practice.

P3, who had more art historical background than most participants, framed the practical argument directly: *"Everything has been made already. You're not gonna come up with original ideas. So the least you can do is steal well, and if you already have the knowledge where to steal from, it might make your journey a little bit easier."* While this reflects a participant who already engages with art history actively, the underlying idea, that broader knowledge may expand available creative resources, resonated with sentiments expressed by other participants. P5, for example, described the encounter as potentially leading them to *"seek broader inspiration than the things I normally look up."* P7 similarly argued: *"How can you become the best at what you do without knowing what other people make?"*

4.3.3.5 The intermediary-reference mechanism

The most analytically interesting pattern in this theme concerns how those connections were bridged. When participants articulated practical connections, these at times involved an intermediary reference, a game or other digital media they had encountered that had already demonstrated a similar aesthetic in a digital context. P8's pathway is illustrative: they connected a Monet painting to Disco Elysium (ZA/UM, 2019) to their own project. The game served as proof of concept that traditional aesthetics could work digitally, which in turn made the traditional source feel more applicable. The traditional painting did not function directly as inspiration; it functioned as inspiration once a digital intermediary had demonstrated that the aesthetic was transferable.

This connects back to the identity work in Theme 1. Participants who described themselves more readily as designers or makers than as artists also tended to articulate connections in terms of how a traditional aesthetic could be reproduced in their medium rather than why the original artist made the choices they did. The intermediary reference might work for the same reason: a game with painterly aesthetics demonstrates the how, which aligns with the question the maker-framed practitioner is already asking. Practical connection, when it appeared, therefore tended to surface as a question about execution rather than about meaning.

This intermediary-reference bridge speaks directly to the knowledge transfer literature (Section 2.4.1). That literature describes near transfer (within similar domains) as more reliable than far transfer (across distinct domains). Sala and Gobet's (2017) meta-analysis find far transfer between unrelated fields rare, while near transfer within similar domains produces more

consistent outcomes. The intermediary-reference pattern observed here suggests a possible mechanism for converting what would otherwise be far transfer (traditional painting to digital game art) into a chain of near transfers (traditional painting to similar-aesthetic game; similar-aesthetic game to one's own game). Each step in the chain is a smaller dimensional gap than the whole, and the intermediary game serves as a translation point bridging the medium and contextual distances between the original traditional source and the practitioner's own work.

This reading is interpretive and goes beyond what the data directly establishes. What the data supports is the more modest observation that intermediary references appeared in several participants' descriptions of how they connected to traditional sources but it was not universal. Participants who reported no relevance (P9, P2) did not describe trying and failing to find intermediary references; they described the source as simply not relevant. Whether intermediaries actually enable transfer, and whether deliberately providing such intermediary references could support transfer from art history to game art more reliably, would require further research designed specifically to test that hypothesis.

A final note about what kind of connections participants identified, with or without an intermediary. When asked what they could take away from the post-impressionist works, participants most often named relatively surface-level elements: colour choices, brushwork, the 'vibe' or atmosphere of a piece, and occasional technique-level observations. Less often did they articulate take-aways at the level of deeper meaning, narrative intent, or the relationship between formal choices and the artist's expressive purpose. This is interesting in light of two patterns already discussed. The purpose-framing distinction from Theme 1 may suggest that if game art is understood as having an external purpose and fine art an internal one, the take-aways that translate most readily across that boundary are precisely those that do not require working with the internal-purpose framing, namely the surface-level visual elements that can be lifted and re-used in another purpose-frame. The vocabulary pattern from Theme 2 might reinforce this: participants with little structured opportunity to analyse visual art reached more readily for elements nameable at a glance. The deeper interpretive material that visual elicitation is designed to surface *was* being surfaced during the looking itself; what was less often happening was its translation into participants' own work.

The observations about surface level take-aways and limited prior analysis training converge on the question of educational application, which several participants raised themselves. When asked whether art history should have a place in game art education, responses were near-unanimous: yes, in some form. What participants struggled with was how. The most consistent recommendation was that any inclusion should focus on learning to look at and discuss art rather than memorising artists, dates, and movements; a framing several explicitly tied to their negative experiences of school art history (echoing P4's expectation of being corrected, discussed in Section 4.3.1.3). Several suggested a non-mandatory module students could opt into based on interest; others argued the opposite, that exposure should be mandatory, reasoning that those who would benefit most were precisely those least likely to seek it out. The split itself was informative: even participants who valued the encounter could not converge on how to make it institutionally workable.

If take-aways come most easily at the surface level, the educational priority participants themselves named, learning to look and discuss rather than memorise artists and dates, is precisely the one that would, possibly, deepen the available pool of take-aways. The data presented here can not establish that such training would definitively have this effect. What it does show is a consistent configuration: participants had limited prior training in analysing

traditional art, their take-aways stayed largely surface-level, and yet there was a near-unanimous, if conditional, sense that this is something curricula could, and probably should, address.

The five observations developed across this theme, the narrowness of current reference pools, medium distance as a variable rather than a fixed barrier, the honest uncertainty some participants expressed about whether art history is worthwhile at all, the patterns visible in where connections were made, and the possible intermediary-reference mechanism together suggest that whether and how an art historical encounter feels applicable to game art practice depends on conditions that vary across participants. The encounter did not produce uniform results. What it did produce, for some participants and not others, was a set of specific practical connections, at times enabled by intermediary references, that bridge the dimensional gap between traditional and digital practice.

4.4 A CROSS-CUTTING OBSERVATION

The three themes presented above each developed a distinct strand of the data: how participants positioned themselves in relation to art, what they did when looking, and whether and how they envisioned the encounter applying to their own practice. One pattern ran across all three and is worth consolidating here. This observation is not a separate finding but a way of seeing the same data at a higher level, a pattern that becomes more visible when the themes are read together.

Across the three themes, one observation appeared repeatedly under different guises: the encounter's value for participants varied substantially, and that variation was not random. Theme 1 documented an unexpected freedom available to some participants (P5.2) alongside the felt deficit experienced by others. Theme 2 documented sustained engagement that surfaced new responses for some participants while producing no perceived shift for others (P9, P2, P4). Theme 3 documented practical connections that some participants saw immediately (P8, P10) and others did not see at all (P9). The same encounter produced different outcomes for different participants, and the cross-theme pattern suggests this variation might reflect something more than random differences in receptivity.

Three dimensions of variation are visible in the data. First, prior engagement with art appears to matter, though not in the simple direction one might expect. Participants with more prior art engagement (P3, P1, P11) sometimes showed deeper engagement but also showed more developed identity work: they had more to be evaluated against, which complicated the affective experience. Participants with less prior engagement (P5.2, P9) sometimes showed less developed vocabulary but were not therefore less perceptive. The relationship between prior art engagement and the encounter's affective and creative consequences is shaped by what Bourdieu (1984) described as cultural capital, but the data suggests this capital functions ambivalently, sometimes enabling deeper engagement and sometimes producing the burden of expectation.

Second, the framing of the encounter appears to matter. Theme 1's freedom-versus-deficit pattern was about the same absence of art history being experienced differently depending on whether it was framed as evaluative (school art history, expected expertise) or non-evaluative (informal looking, unargued opinion). As Section 4.3.2 showed, the sustained-engagement finding was framed by the structured visual elicitation method: prolonged looking and probing dialogue produced effects that participants reported not getting in their typical unguided museum visits. And as Section 4.3.3 showed, practical connections sometimes required an intermediary reference to feel applicable. In each case, the encounter's value depended substantially on how it was structured rather than on the encounter alone.

Third, disciplinary specialty appears to matter, though more lightly. The default modes of engagement, discussed in Section 4.3.2, corresponded loosely to disciplinary focus, technique-first observation among environment and prop specialists, narrative-first among those with narrative or character focus. These defaults shaped what participants noticed and what they treated as applicable. Different specialisms appear to bring different evaluative orientations, and what counts as relevant from a post-impressionist work might look different depending on what one's focus is within their own creative practice.

These three dimensions do not combine into a single tidy causal explanation. They interact, and how they interact for any given participant cannot be predicted from the data this study collected. What can be said is that the encounter's value is conditional rather than uniform: it

depends on what the participant brings, how the encounter is framed, and what they are making. The patterns documented across these three themes provide qualitative material on the boundary between art history and game art education, gathered from the perspective of students and recent alumni themselves: participants' perception and engagement with the works shifted for many (Themes 1 and 2), while a shift in their creative practice was less clear (Theme 3). Where practical connection did appear, it was often surface-level and at times mediated through intermediary references rather than translating directly from source to practice. Ludwig and Boyle's (2017) characterisation of arts-exposure effects as "statistically significant but modest in magnitude" fits the picture here: the encounter produced something for many participants, but what it produced was incremental and partial rather than transformative. This conditional framing shapes how the findings should be read and for what kinds of pedagogical or research moves might productively follow, both of which are taken up further in the Conclusion.

4.5 LIMITATIONS AND REFLEXIVE CONSIDERATIONS

The findings presented in this chapter should be read with several limitations in mind. This section consolidates the limitations that arose throughout the study, drawing together points that have already been named in their thematic contexts throughout the chapter and adding those that warrant their own space, along with the steps taken to mitigate them where possible. The aim of this chapter is not to undermine the findings but to position them truthfully.

4.5.1 Sample and recruitment limitations

The primary sample consisted of eleven game art students and recent alumni, with an additional four re-interviews. This is a sample size appropriate for qualitative exploratory research aiming for depth rather than breadth, but it does limit generalisability. This sample size was anticipated within the project's timeframe and argued for in the methodology chapter (Section 3.3): qualitative exploratory work prioritises analytical depth per participant over breadth. Findings should therefore be understood as indicating patterns worth further investigation rather than as definitive claims applicable to all game art students.

The sample was recruited through the researcher's professional and personal networks, with participants drawn predominantly from one institution (HKU, Utrecht University of the Arts). This educational concentration again constrains transferability. Game art programmes vary in curriculum, culture, and student demographic, and the patterns documented here may not transfer cleanly to populations from different programmes or institutions. The concentrated sample was a consequence of the networks available to the researcher; it may have shaped the data more than the analysis could surface, and it directly motivates the replication across institutions recommended and explained further in Section 5.2. Patterns specific to HKU's approach, for example, the kinds of disciplinary specialisations the programme cultivates, may be implicit in the data without having been examined or discussed explicitly.

The participants also shared a Dutch educational and cultural context. Cross-cultural variation in how art history is taught, valued, and integrated into creative education almost certainly shaped responses in ways outside the current study's scope. The researcher was unable to mitigate this limitation, so it is acknowledged as a boundary on transferability and as a recommendation for future research (see 5.2). Findings may not transfer to game art programmes in other national contexts where art history occupies a different position in cultural and educational life.

4.5.2 Methodological limitations

The study captured participants' responses at a single point in time, supplemented by re-interviews conducted relatively shortly after the initial encounter. Longer-term effects of the encounter on participants' actual creative practice remain unassessed. This was difficult to mitigate and was accepted as a feature of the design: single-encounter studies with short follow-ups are, as the literature makes clear, poorly suited to capturing durable effects. P1.2's reported behaviour change (starting workdays with art, Section 4.3.2) was the only reported behavioural shift, and it was self-reported rather than independently observed. Whether the reported shifts in intention or openness translated into durable changes in practice over months or years was beyond what this study set out to establish.

The researcher-curated image selection, by a non-expert in post-impressionism, and the reduction from four-to-six images to three, also constrained the encounter. Different image

selections, by other researchers, by art historians, or by the participants themselves, would likely have produced different findings, and using fewer images limited the variety of post-impressionist material participants saw. Both were practical necessities given the interview duration and the master's timeframe.

Visual elicitation is designed to prompt reflection on visual material, and the researcher's questions could have directed attention towards potential meaning and relevance. The risk is (like briefly touched upon in Section 3.7) therefore that the researcher may, unintentionally, have steered participants toward particular readings, or that participants' prior expectations about the study's purpose coloured their responses. This was mitigated through using open, non-leading questions (reviewed with peers before data collection) and by repeatedly reconfirming the researcher's interpretation against the data throughout the process. The possibility of social desirability bias, or of unintentional steering, is acknowledged as a limitation tied to both the researcher's limited experience and the chosen research method of interviewing.

The remote interview format also shapes what the encounter could be. Looking at artworks through a screen removes the experience of encountering art in person, including factors such as scale, texture, material presence, and what Benjamin (1935) termed the "aura" of the original work. These qualities were lost in digital reproduction, which may have diminished the richness of participants' encounters. This was a practical necessity given the remote format and the geographic spread of participants, and it is acknowledged as a genuine loss. At the same time, screen-based viewing arguably reflects the most realistic way this group would ordinarily encounter such works. Whether the patterns documented in this chapter would hold for in-person encounters with original works in a gallery setting nonetheless remains unknown.

The analysis was conducted primarily through repeated listening to audio recordings rather than through systematic software-supported coding in MAXQDA. As described in Section 4.2, this choice was made for analytical responsiveness to tone, hesitation, and emphasis, but it traded off against the systematic code-frequency tracking and visual code mapping that software would have facilitated. The trade-off was small and deliberate but should still be acknowledged.

The interviews were conducted in Dutch, with one exception conducted in English. All quotations presented in this chapter were translated by the researcher, with the original Dutch quotes available in Appendix F. The translation from Dutch to English introduces the possibility of nuance being lost or shifted, particularly where idiomatic expressions carry specific cultural weight. The Dutch phrases preserved in the text ("*kunst met een grote K*," "*ambacht*," "*zweverig*," "*saaie*," "*opgeplakt*") are precisely those whose meaning resists clean English substitution. Because all but one interview were conducted and analysed in Dutch, reinterpretation of the dataset is realistically open only to Dutch-reading researchers, which limits its reuse by a wider audience. Translation was nonetheless the methodologically recommended choice (Section 3.5), since offering participants their preferred language protects data quality. The limitation is best understood as a noted consequence, translation can shift nuance, but it is not a significant threat to validity.

4.5.3 Analytical limitations

The recursive design of the analysis meant that later interviews and the re-interviews were partly informed by patterns emerging from earlier analysis. This recursive structure is consistent with Reflexive Thematic Analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019), as described in Sections

4.2.1 and 4.2.2, which supports that the data and the themes co-developed rather than the themes being derived from a fixed dataset. A limitation that arose from this is that patterns that surfaced later in the data collection or analysis could not be explored in as much depth as desired. The earlier theme of identity, for example, was more thoroughly discussed through re-interviews than the later cross-cutting pattern around intermediary references. Because the recursive structure is an expected feature of Reflexive Thematic Analysis rather than a deviation from it, this limitation weighs relatively lightly.

Several patterns identified in this chapter rest on small numbers of participants. The spatial discomfort observation was most clearly articulated by P11 and P7 in response to one specific work. P5.2's freedom-from-expectation counter-finding was articulated by one participant. P10's expressionism-for-a-game concrete example is a single case. This is a familiar limitation of small-scale qualitative work; it was addressed by engaging each observation in as much analytical depth as the data allowed, and by hedging single-participant claims explicitly throughout. Readers should understand these found patterns as observations from this sample, not established or generalizable findings.

That participants who articulated the echo chamber most clearly were also those with stronger prior art engagement, applies more broadly across the chapter. The participants who articulated the patterns most explicitly tended to be those with more prior reflection on their practice or more developed self-direction, which means the data is partly weighted towards what reflective practitioners can name. This was mitigated by deliberately attending to the less articulate or less polished responses as well as the quotable ones; working from the audio rather than transcripts alone helped here, since it surfaced how participants said things, not just what they said.

Several of these limitations map directly onto the recommended future research directions set out in the Conclusion chapter of this study (Section 5.2).

4.5.4 Reflexive considerations

The researcher's positionality as a game art practitioner with a personal interest in the role of art history in game art education is acknowledged in detail in Section 3.7.2, and the strategies for managing the associated risks (open-ended question design, attention to disconfirming data, peer debriefing) are described there. What follows here is brief and specific to the analytical stage of the work, rather than a restatement of those strategies.

During the analysis, several specific moments where reflexive attention shaped the interpretation are worth noting. The decision to include negative cases (P9 most clearly, but also P2, P4, and the spatial discomfort observation's framing of game-art-trained perception as potentially limiting) was made deliberately rather than treating these responses as outliers. The hedging language throughout the chapter ("may suggest," "one reading worth considering," "this study cannot resolve") is part of the same effort to keep claims appropriately scoped.

A limitation specifically related to the researcher's positionality is the fact that this research was designed, conducted and analysed by a single researcher. This places all interpretive decisions with one person and admits the possibility of bias, including subconscious bias, at every stage from coding to write-up; the peer debriefing and disconfirming-case strategies described above were the principal counterweights, but they do not eliminate it. Relatedly, not all of the collected data could be discussed in depth. The dataset contains more material than this chapter presents, and decisions about what to foreground were the researcher's own, made under the constraints

of limited experience and a fixed timeframe. Some observations could be pursued further, or with additional sources, than was possible within the scope of this master's thesis.

Qualitative research does not aim to eliminate the researcher's standpoint but to make it visible and accountable (Berger, 2015; Braun & Clarke, 2019). Readers should understand the findings as having been produced through this particular lens, with the strategies described above as deliberate efforts to keep that lens from distorting the analysis beyond what reflexivity makes possible.

5 CONCLUSION

5.1 RETURNING TO THE RESEARCH QUESTION

This study set out to investigate the following question:

How do game art students and recent alumni perceive and make meaning from post-impressionist visual techniques and historical context, and how do they relate this encounter to their creative process and design outcomes?

The three themes developed in the Findings and Discussion chapter: Identity, Engagement, and Practical Application, each address a different part of the research question, and read together they support a two-part answer.

On the first part of the question, this study found that participants seemed to perceive and make meaning from post-impressionist material primarily through the lens of their own creative identity. They did not appear to approach the encounter from a neutral starting point. As the theme of Identity documented, they came to it by their own account as outsiders to the fine-art world, partitioning their own practice from 'real' art on the basis of purpose, and experiencing the absence of art history from their education not as neutral missing information but as something felt: shame and a sense of deficit for most, but, more unexpectedly, a kind of freedom for one participant. They also brought design-shaped evaluative orientations to the act of looking, namely innovation, narrative, craft, and personal connection. As the Engagement theme showed, these orientations seemed to work as both enabling and constraining filters: they directed attention toward features that aligned with what participants already valued, but at times produced discomfort or disinterest when a work violated trained expectations, as with the spatial "wrongness" several participants registered in the Van Gogh. Meaning-making, on this reading, was filtered through identity as much as it was shaped by the artwork.

What participants brought, however, was not the whole picture, because how the encounter was staged also seemed to change what they could do with it. Vocabulary, for one, functioned as a resource for articulation rather than as a measure of perceptiveness: participants frequently appeared to see more than their available language let them name. Sustained, open-ended looking surfaced responses participants did not seem to expect, and the staged provision of historical context deepened or reframed initial readings for several of them. That structured looking and probing dialogue draw out such responses echoes what Visual Thinking Strategies (Yenawine, 2013), discussed in the literature review, has documented in general audiences; what this study adds is the tentative observation that the same pattern appears in a population that already engages with visuals regularly. This observation points to a possible value in more consciously teaching game art students to look at and discuss art, particularly material from outside their habitual reference pool: it may offer a route out of the self-referential 'echo chamber' introduced in Chapter 1, and could let students draw on unfamiliar sources they might otherwise do little with.

On the second part of the question, participants related the encounter to their creative practice across a wide spectrum, running from immediate practical connection to reasoned, honest disinterest. Where connections were made, they tended to cluster at a relatively surface level, in colour, painterly aesthetics, and atmosphere, rather than, for example, in the relationship between an artist's formal choices and their expressive intent, which might be explained by the purpose-based artist/maker partition discussed under the Identity theme. One observation

about practical connection stood out in particular: the connection at times seemed to arrive indirectly. A traditional source felt more usable once a familiar game had already demonstrated a similar aesthetic working in a digital context, a pattern this study refers to as the intermediary reference and develops under the Practical Application theme. The clearest instance was a participant for whom a Monet painting became better translatable into their own 3D project largely by way of *Disco Elysium*, a game with a similarly painterly style. Read against the transfer literature reviewed in Chapter 2, this tentatively suggests, without establishing, that the difficult far transfer from traditional painting to digital game art can in practice occur as a chain of more manageable near transfers.

Taken together, the study's answer to its research question is that game art students and recent alumni do perceive, make meaning from, and can draw on post-impressionist material, but conditionally rather than uniformly. Participants did appear to perceive and make meaning fairly readily, but through identity and training rather than as blank receivers; and they did relate the encounter to their own creative practice, but unevenly, often only at the surface and at times only by way of a bridge. As the cross-cutting observation in the discussion set out, this conditionality seemed to depend on what participants brought to the encounter, on how it was framed, and on their disciplinary focus. Ludwig & Boyle (2017) characterisation of arts-exposure effects as real but modest fits the picture well: something seemed to happen for many participants, but it was incremental rather than transformative. This in turn reframes the productive question for the field from whether art-historical encounters benefit game art students towards under what conditions and for whom, and what structures might support transfer when it occurs.

5.2 CONTRIBUTIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This study makes four contributions to the under-researched intersection of art history and game art education, each exploratory, and each opening a corresponding direction for further work. Because the answer the study reaches is a conditional one, the most useful future research may be less confirmatory than specifying: an attempt to identify which conditions matter, and how much. Several of the directions below also respond to the limitations set out in the discussion, which are drawn on here rather than restated.

The first two contributions concern what the study did and how. Most concretely, it offers small-scale qualitative evidence on how game art students and recent alumni encounter and respond to post-impressionist art, addressing an empirical absence where almost none existed before. The way that evidence was gathered may be a contribution in its own right: visual elicitation is well established in qualitative research, but had not, to this researcher's knowledge, been applied to game art practitioners engaging with art-historical material. The design developed here, which combined researcher- and participant-selected images, structured probing during sustained looking, and the staged provision of context, produced rich data on a population that had been little studied, and its refinements and constraints are set out in the discussion so that others might anticipate them rather than rediscover them. Since the patterns reported here come from a small sample drawn predominantly from one institution and a single Dutch context, a natural next step would be replication with larger and more varied samples across different institutions and national settings, which might help test whether these patterns are features of game art education more broadly or of this particular setting, while also helping to

confirm the findings that currently rest on only one or two participants, such as the freedom-from-expectation counter-finding.

The other two contributions are more a matter of the ideas the study produced. The first, and perhaps its most prominent finding, is conceptual: that participants seemed to approach the encounter primarily through identity work, something that was not anticipated at the outset and that the Identity theme develops into a substantive lens on how game art practitioners meet art-historical material. This is offered as a starting point for further research to build on, refine, or contest, and it points toward one direction in particular. Because the same absence of art history seemed to produce shame in some participants and a kind of freedom in others, depending on how it was framed, a study that varied how an encounter is introduced, evaluative versus non-evaluative, might help show whether *how* art history is presented matters as much as *whether* it is. The second idea is more speculative: the intermediary-reference mechanism, which tentatively suggests that what looks like difficult far transfer between distant creative domains may in practice occur through chains of more manageable near transfer, mediated by familiar translation points. The data here supports the existence of the pattern but cannot establish the mechanism, which makes it a natural candidate for closer testing; a study comparing traditional sources shown alone against the same sources paired with familiar digital intermediaries might show whether the mechanism genuinely enables transfer or merely tends to accompany it. Were that the case, the pedagogical implication would be fairly concrete, namely that such encounters may be more productive when traditional sources are bridged by digital examples.

A few final directions follow from the study as a whole rather than from any single contribution. Because it was designed, conducted, and analysed by a single researcher, the expert-review stage that could not be completed within the project's timeframe could later add a useful layer of practitioner triangulation. And because the single-encounter design left the durability of any effect unassessed, longitudinal work with repeated encounters over time would help establish whether the reported shifts in intention or openness tend to last. This last point connects to a broader ambition that shaped the early stages of the project but ultimately fell outside its scope: the development of a practical tool or resource to help game artists engage with and learn from art history more systematically, such as a structured looking-and-discussion resource, or a curated reference set that deliberately pairs art-historical works with digital intermediaries in the manner this study describes. Building and evaluating such a tool, ideally across repeated use, could be a natural way to take the conditional findings of this study and test whether they translate into something of practical pedagogical value, addressing the questions of durability and applicability together.

5.3 CLOSING REFLECTION

This thesis began with a small and personal observation: the absence of art history from a bachelor's programme in game art, and the sense among fellow classmates that something potentially valuable was missing. Framing that observation as a research question quickly revealed how little empirical evidence existed on this interdisciplinary intersection. Answering the larger question, whether art history should be part of game art education, proved too big a gap to close within this project's scope; the work had to start smaller. The aim became to explore what actually happens when game art students and recent alumni encounter art-historical material, and to gather evidence where assumption had largely been standing in for it: an early, grounded step into a much larger and still largely open question.

So, the honest answer this study can offer is a conditional one: sometimes, for some participants, under some framings, the encounter seemed to open new ways of looking and to make unfamiliar work feel usable; for others it remained foreign, interesting perhaps, but not relevant to their practice. That is a more modest claim than the project first imagined, but perhaps still a useful one, since it turns a yes-or-no question into a set of conditions that can, and arguably should, be examined more closely. What this study contributes is a first mapping of territory that had gone largely unexamined: some evidence where there had been assumption, and a set of conditions worth testing further. It does not resolve whether art history belongs in game art education, but it may map enough of the ground that the researchers, educators, and practitioners who come next have somewhere to begin.

APPENDIX A

RESEARCHER-SELECTED IMAGES

This appendix presents the six post-impressionist works selected as visual stimuli for the study, together with full-resolution reproduction details and source links. The works are listed in the fixed order in which they were presented to participants (see Table 3.1). As noted in Section 4.2.1, time constraints meant most interviews used the first three works.

Bathers, by P. Cézanne, Oil on Canvas, 1874-75, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/435867>

Circus Sideshow (Parade de cirque), by G. Seurat, Oil on Canvas, ca. 1887, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/437654>

Oleanders, by V. van Gogh, Oil on Canvas, 1888, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/436530>

The Repast of the Lion, by H. Rousseau, Oil on Canvas, ca. 1907, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/438822>

Steamboats in the Port of Rouen, by C. Pissarro, Oil on Canvas, 1896, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/437309>

Still Life with Teapot and Fruit, by P. Gauguin, Oil on Canvas, 1896, The Metropolitan Museum of Art

<https://www.metmuseum.org/art/collection/search/437999>

APPENDIX B

PARTICIPANT BRIEFING DOCUMENT AND CONSENT FORM

This appendix contains the two documents provided to participants prior to their interview. The first is the briefing document, instructing each participant to select two artworks for discussion during Stage 2: one work that had influenced their thinking or practice as a game artist, and one traditional painting that held personal meaning. The second is the consent form, built from the BUAs-provided template, outlining how participation, recording, data storage, and anonymisation were handled, which participants reviewed and agreed to before the interview began. Both documents are referenced in Section 3.4.2.

B.1 Participant Briefing Document

Participant Briefing Document

Thank you for agreeing to participate in this research study. This document quickly explains what to expect and what I'd like you to prepare before our interview.

About the Study

This study is part of my master's thesis at Breda University of Applied Sciences (BUAs). It explores how game art students and recent graduates experience, respond and discuss traditional artworks during an art encounter.

During the interview, we will look at and discuss several artworks together. I am interested in your real, personal responses and experiences. There are no right or wrong answers and it's not a knowledge test, your perspective is my data.

What to Expect

The interview will take place online via Microsoft Teams and will last approximately 60 to 90 minutes. It will be recorded (audio, screen and video) with your consent. Video recording serves as a backup to help clarify responses if the audio or transcript is unclear. All recordings will be stored securely and only be accessible to myself and my supervisors.

During the interview you are welcome to sketch or make visual notes if you find that helpful, using whatever tools you prefer (paper, tablet, drawing software). This is entirely optional but if you did, I would like you to share these sketches or notes with me.

I will share a file containing the artworks we will discuss at the start of the interview. This is so you can view them comfortably on your own screen at full resolution, and adjust display settings or zoom in as you wish.

The interview will be conducted in either Dutch or English, whichever you are most comfortable with. Please let me know your preference before or when we start the interview.

What I'd Like You to Prepare

Before the interview, I would like you to select two artworks and send them to me. Please try to do this before our interview, so I can have them ready to display during our conversation.

Artwork 1: An artwork of your choice that has influenced your thinking or practice as a game artist. This can be anything, fine art, illustration, concept art, a screenshot from a game, or anything else that has been meaningful to your creative work.

Artwork 2: A traditional artwork, preferably a painting although other traditional media are accepted as well, that holds meaning for you. This can be any artwork or painting from any period or style.

Please send me either the image files or links to the images.

A note on choosing your images

Choose whatever feels right to you. Try not to overthink it, your first instinct is valuable, and there is no "correct" choice. If you do find yourself deliberating between options or going through a longer thought process, feel free to jot down a few notes about that process. How you arrived at your choices can be just as interesting as the choices themselves, and we shall briefly discuss it during the interview.

Giving consent

You will receive a separate consent form alongside this briefing. Please review and sign it before the interview. The consent form confirms that:

- Your participation is entirely voluntary
- You may withdraw without needing to provide a reason
- All data will be anonymised. Your name, age, and gender will not be collected
- If you wish to withdraw after the interview, any data collected from your session will be removed upon your request.

Questions?

A Qualitative Exploration of How Game Art Students Engage with Art Historical Material

If you have any questions about the study, the interview, or your participation, please don't hesitate to reach out to me at any time :)

Iza Morel Iodenhamn@gmail.com or 251495@buas.nl Master Game Technology, Breda
University of Applied Sciences

B.2 Consent Form

CONSENT FORM — Master Thesis Interview

Research title: Game art student meaning making of an art encounter

I, (your full name)

provide consent to the following research institution: Breda University of Applied Sciences (BUAs) to use my data within the above-mentioned project.

I have been informed about the research project entitled 'Game art student meaning making of an art encounter' and have been requested to give consent in this form for the data collection and use of the 1 to 1,5 hour long interview, while monitored in a Microsoft Teams meeting.

I have been informed about the goal of this project and I have had the opportunity to ask the research team any questions which may arise about the research and my participation. I understand that my participation in this research is voluntary, I am free to refuse to participate in the research at any time during the interview process and I am aware that I can only withdraw consent until 1 week after the data collection has ended. If I withdraw my consent within this period, all collected data related to my participation will be deleted. My refusal to participate or withdrawal of consent will not affect my position and my relationship with the institutions involved.

If I have any enquiries about the research, I can contact Iza Morel (iodenhamn@gmail.com), the responsible researcher.

By signing below, I am indicating my consent to the following:

- I consent to having this interview audio, video and screen recorded via Microsoft Teams.
- I consent to having the collected data be shared and used for research purposes and related publications.
- I consent to being contacted if further clarification is necessary to investigate statements present in the collected data.

All names will be removed from video, audio and transcriptions collected during the interview. All data presented in the thesis will be presented in an anonymized way.

I understand that the data collected from my participation will be used for the purpose of this research and will be securely stored, and I consent for it to be used in that manner.

Date:

Signature:

APPENDIX C

PILOT INTERVIEW

This appendix documents the pilot interview conducted prior to the main study. Section C.1 summarises the purpose of the pilot, the key methodological refinements that resulted, and preliminary analytical observations. Section C.2 presents a fuller account of the pilot interview data across the interview phases. A condensed account of the pilot's outcomes also appears in the main text; this appendix is referenced in Section 3.4.2.

C.1 Pilot Test and Methodological Refinements

Pilot Test

A pilot test of the methodology was conducted to ensure relevant data could be collected and to refine the protocols for both participant and researcher. A more detailed description of the pilot interview is described in the Details of Experiment, Data and Results chapter. Here the focus is on the key takeaways from the pilot and how they affected the final methodology.

Although this methodology was grounded in established approaches and had support from existing literature, it required testing within this specific context. The pilot test took place during the winter break and was conducted online, lasting approximately two and a half hours. Despite it bringing to light several points of improvement, the pilot seemed to demonstrate preliminary evidence that his method is able to collect meaningful data to answer the research question.

Several refinements resulted from the pilot. First the number of images shown during phase 3 of the interview was reduced. The participant reported visual fatigue, and the overall duration was much longer than anticipated and desired. As a result, the planned number of images was reduced from six to eight to four to six. Second, the selection of images was adjusted based on the researcher's observation of unintentional bias towards certain themes and colour schemes which contradicted the intention to present deliberate variety in artists, themes, and styles. Additionally, to improve accessibility, it was decided that images will be provide to participants in a digital file prior to the interview, rather than relying solely on screen sharing. This allows participants to view the high-resolution versions and accommodate those who want to adjust display settings or, for example, zoom in.

Third, the interview questions were refined. Although the semi-structured format remains open to following the natural flow of the conversation, some new questions emerged during the pilot that have been incorporated into the standard protocol, and others were adjusted to attempt to elicit deeper responses. Related to this, the pilot highlighted the importance of being aware of what participants focus on when describing artworks and prompting for specifics when needed. In the pilot, the participant focused mostly on interpretation, so it was noted that specific probes for more literal observation may be needed with this type of participant to gather rich and comprehensive data.

Finally, several procedural refinements were made to help the interview flow more smoothly and to prepare participants better beforehand. These include using a two-screen setup during the interview, providing a clear briefing document to send to participants in advance and asking participants for their preferred language at the start of the interview. This last point introduces

a limitation, as translations may cause misunderstandings in how data is described. However, allowing participants to choose their preferred language gives them the opportunity to express themselves more comfortably, which may yield richer responses.

Despite the refinements needed, the pilot demonstrated that using this methodology can elicit rich data relevant to the research question. Since one pilot cannot be expected to catch everything, the first interviews of the main study will also be treated as opportunities for further methodological refinement.

Preliminary Analytical Observations

While the full thematic analysis will follow after more interviews are conducted, the pilot data offers preliminary indications that the methodology generates relevant findings.

The participant consistently described visual elements, particularly compositional features suggesting narrative and colour relationships. However, formal vocabulary was limited, techniques were mentioned but without specific terminology. Highlighting how this methodology can capture related themes if this pattern persists.

Historical context shifted the participant's understanding in notable ways. Information about Cézanne's relationship with his models transformed an intuitive observation ("the figures look pasted in") into a historically grounded interpretation, indicating the methodology can capture how contextual information affects perception.

The participant demonstrated an "interpretive-first" approach, gravitating toward narrative meaning-making before formal analysis. This pattern may reflect their self-identified focus on narrative in their own work, suggesting that existing creative values shape engagement with unfamiliar artworks.

Finally, the participant articulated both connections and distinctions between the encountered works and their own practice, identifying resonance with works conveying narratives or capturing emotions while noting that traditional techniques would not transfer directly to digital practice. The metaphor of a "seed" being planted suggests the methodology captures subtle forms of influence even if they may not manifest as direct technical adoption.

These preliminary observations will be checked and refined through analysis of subsequent interviews. The pilot suggests the methodology can surface patterns relevant to the research question, though the single-participant data cannot indicate whether these patterns will be consistent across the sample.

C.2 Pilot Interview Data

Participant Background

The participant is a recent game art graduate (bachelor's degree, summer 2025) specializing in character art, 3D sculpting, and related digital techniques. Their higher education started with MBO game development but soon moved toward a visual arts focus, a shift they attribute to recognizing their creative inclinations aligned more with visual expression than programming. They described coming from a creative family but initially dismissing art as a viable path before rediscovering it through peer encouragement.

At the time of the interview, the participant had no formal education in art history during their bachelor's program. They described their relationship with art history as one of interest but minimal engagement "an emmer die goed gevuld kan worden" (a bucket that could be well-filled). They noted that exposure came primarily through self-directed research into the influences of contemporary digital artists they admire rather than through structured curriculum or specific art historical interest.

Personal Artistic Values (Phase 2)

When discussing self-selected inspirational works, the participant emphasized narrative capacity and emotional resonance as primary values. Their chosen digital artwork by Lucas Lima was described as aspirational for its ability to convey extensive story and character depth in a single image. They identified strongly as a "narrative artist," stating that viewer emotional response is the defining criterion for successful artwork: "een goed kunstwerk is een kunstwerk wat emotie opbrengt" (a good artwork is one that evokes emotion).

For traditional art, the participant selected a Bob Ross painting, notably emphasizing the artist's creative philosophy and process over the work's formal or particular visual qualities. This revealed a tendency to connect with art through the creator's intentionality and emotional authenticity rather than the purely visual attributes. They did note that having to pick a traditional artwork was more complicated to them, contributing this to their lack of knowledge and interaction with traditional artworks.

Responses to Post-Impressionist Works (Phase 3)

Four post-impressionist works were viewed: *Bathers* by Cézanne (1874), the final study for *A Sunday on La Grande Jatte* by Georges Seurat (1884), *The Repast of the Lion* by Rousseau (1907), and *Oleanders* by van Gogh (1888).

Across all works, the participant consistently demonstrated an interpretive-first approach, gravitating toward narrative construction and emotional meaning before formal analysis. When viewing Cézanne's *Bathers*, their initial response centred on themes of freedom, autonomy, and peace rather than compositional or technical elements. They described the figures as women who had made free choices, inferring backstory and motivation from posture and setting.

Historical context consistently shifted the participant's perception. Upon learning of Cézanne's documented discomfort with female models, the participant connected this to a previously intuited sense that the figures appeared "opgeplakt" (pasted in), describing that their unconscious formal observation aligned with the historical explanation. Similarly, learning that Seurat's study was preparatory work for a pointillist piece, and that it depicted a deliberate Sunday scene rather than an elite display, reframed the participant's initial class-conscious reading toward appreciation of artistic experimentation.

The Rousseau painting prompted extended reflection on mortality, natural cycles, and interconnectedness, themes the participant explicitly connected to personal philosophical frameworks (citing the anime Fullmetal Alchemist's concept of "all is one"). They also noted the perceptual impact of their colour-blindness on viewing this work, describing difficulty distinguishing certain hues and the resultant altered experience.

With Van Gogh's Oleanders, prior cultural knowledge of the artist influenced perception before formal viewing. The participant identified the work as Van Gogh's based on perceived visual "hallucinations" (faces in the foliage), which they associated with their understanding of Van Gogh's mental health history. Learning the work was a gift intended to symbolize joy and enduring life confirmed rather than altered their interpretation although they did express being surprised about them being correct about it being a Van Gogh painting but deducting so from their interpretation and not the visual style or technique per se.

Connections to Creative Practice (Phase 4)

When asked to relate the encounter to their own work, the participant identified strongest resonance with works that conveyed narrative, particularly Cézanne's Bathers and Rousseau's jungle scene. They also noted that the emotional and philosophical dimensions of artworks (especially Van Gogh's personal history as catalyst for creation) aligned with their own approach of channelling personal experience into creative output.

However, the participant distinguished between inspirational resonance and direct technical transfer. They stated that traditional media do not feel like their working mode, and that they would be unlikely to directly adopt post-impressionist techniques. Instead, they anticipated potential indirect influence: "Ik zou liegen als het geen invloed heeft, dat heeft het zeker" (I'd be lying if it had no influence, it definitely does). They framed the encounter as having planted a "seed" that might affect future creative directions in ways not yet fully conscious.

The participant concluded that the session had increased their interest in art history, describing it as revealing how much they did not know and motivating further self-directed exploration. They expressed that they would now be better able to recognize post-impressionist works in a gallery context and would approach these works with new contextual understanding which excited them.

The methodological refinements resulting from this pilot are detailed in the Methodology chapter 3.6. Key changes included reducing the number of researcher-selected images from six-eight to four-six based on observed visual fatigue, adjusting image selection to reduce researcher bias and ensure greater variety in themes and colour schemes, and refining interview questions to balance the participants natural responses with prompts for specific formal observation if needed.

Importantly, while the pilot revealed areas for methodological refinement, it also demonstrated that the core approach, visual elicitation combined with contextual information provision, can generate rich data relevant to the components of the research question. The participant's responses showed evidence of perception (describing visual elements), contextualisation (responding to historical information), interpretation (making meaning from artistic choices), and resonance (connecting the encounter to their own creative practice). This provides confidence that the final methodology will enable meaningful data collection across the full participant sample.

APPENDIX D

INTERVIEW GUIDES

This appendix contains the two semi-structured interview guides used in the study. Section D.1 presents the primary interview guide following the five-stage structure described in Section 3.5.1; Section D.2 presents the shorter re-interview guide used for the four follow-up interviews. Both are referenced in Sections 3.5.1 and 4.2.1.

D.1 Primary Interview Guide

Final Version Interview Guide (English)

A guide to provide structure and consistency when conducting interviews. The semi-structured interview consists of follow-up questions and participant-specific questions, allowing the questions in this document to be adapted or rephrased during the interview.

Important reminders for the researcher:

- Watch for opportunities to reference participants' earlier statements later in the interview
- Monitor whether participants tend more toward interpretation or formal observation, and ask questions about the underrepresented dimension
- Not every question needs to be asked for every image in Phase 3; essential and rotating questions are marked as such
- Note striking phrasings from participants in their own words for use in Phase 4
- Give participants silence/thinking time after answering before moving on to the next question

Phase 1: Background (5–10 minutes)

Introduce to people that we're starting with a kind of background/baseline check.

Core questions:

1. Can you tell me something about your background, education, work, and/or specialisation?
2. How do you see yourself / which label or description best fits how you see yourself in your field?
 - a. Follow-up (if relevant): Does that label change depending on the context, for example at school versus at work or in conversation with outsiders?
 - b. How do you describe/explain to people outside the industry what you do/make or what you are/your label?
3. When you're working on a project, where do you usually look for visual references or inspiration? What does that process look like for you?
4. When you make visual choices in your work/own creative process, do you consciously think about these choices? If so, in what way, and what guides you in that?
5. How would you describe your familiarity with/knowledge of traditional art or art history? Is it something that comes back in your work or studies?

6. Follow-up (if needed): Can you think of a moment when you encountered a traditional artwork, in whatever context: a museum, online, in the references of a game? What was that like?
 - a. Follow-up (if needed): What does “art history” mean to you? (Only use if their answer points to an unusual or very narrow definition that could influence later answers.)

Phase 2: Participant-Selected Images (15–20 minutes)

Core questions:

1. Before we look at it closely, can you tell me what attracted you to this work or what your reason was for selecting it?
2. Now, tell me what you see here, what stands out to you most, what do you think, what do you feel?
3. What is important to you about this image? (if they haven’t already answered)
4. Can you describe/explain what it does, for example technically or visually, that attracts or attracted you to this work?
 - a. Follow-up: What is it precisely about [named thing] that works for you?
5. What does it mean to you? What associations, feelings, or perhaps inspiration does it evoke for you?
6. (After discussing both images) How do these two works relate to each other for you, or do they feel quite separate?
7. What was it like selecting these images? What was your process? Did you approach them differently?
 - a. Follow-up (if relevant): Was one easier to choose than the other? Why do you think that was?
8. When you think about the paintings I’m about to show you, what do you actually expect? How do you think it will be for you, and why?

Follow-up prompts (use where needed):

- Tell me a bit more about that.
- Can you say a bit more about what you mean by [x]?
- You mentioned [x], what is it about that precisely?
- Is there anything else that stands out to you?
- How did you arrive at that reading/interpretation? (Focuses on the meaning-making process, not just the result.)

Phase 3: Researcher-Selected Images (30–40 minutes, repeat for each of the 3 to 4 images)

Essential questions (ask with every image):

1. Take a moment to look. When you’re ready, describe what you see, feel, and think at first glance.
2. What stands out to you most here (besides the things you’ve already mentioned)?
3. How do you interpret this image? What associations does this image evoke for you?

[Provide context: artist, title, date, and 2–3 sentences of contextual information]

4. Now that you know this context, does knowing this change anything for you?
 - a. Follow-up: Does this information connect to something you noticed earlier, before I shared the context? Or does it change your interpretation of the image, what you get from it, or something else?

5. What is your overall reaction to this work? Or how would you summarise or explain your own reaction to this work to someone else?

Formal observation follow-ups (deploy when participants default toward interpretation):

- Could you describe what you notice about how colour is used here?
- How would you describe the way this is painted, for example, the technique itself?
- What is happening with the composition or the arrangement of elements?
- If you focus only on how this looks rather than what it means, what do you see?

Rotating deepening questions (vary across images, use 1–2 per image):

- Is there something within this work that attracts you, or that you actually resist?
- How does this relate to the other images we've looked at so far?
- Is there something about this work you'd like to understand better? Or is there something about it that raises questions, whether about content or technique?
- Is there something about this work that reminds you of work you know, from games or elsewhere?
- If you saw this work hanging in a museum, how would you engage with it?

Practical application questions (ask with at least 2 of the images):

- If this image were in your reference folder, for which project or what kind of problem would you use it? What would you concretely take from it?
- How do you think you respond to this work compared to someone with a different creative background, for example, a graphic designer, an illustrator, or a student at a traditional art school? What would be different, if anything?
- Or: Do you think your background as a game artist influences how you look at this work or what you take from it? If so, how? Would someone with a different creative background approach it differently, do you think?

Process follow-ups (use occasionally to capture the meaning-making process):

- What led you to that reading?
- How did you arrive at that interpretation?

Phase 4: Synthesis and Creative Resonance (15–20 minutes)

Opening reflection:

1. How was it for you to engage so intensively with these paintings today? Did it feel like something familiar, something strange, or something else and where do you think that feeling comes from?
 - a. What role does art play for you? Inspiration, or...?
2. Looking back at the images we discussed, were there images that particularly stayed with you, or that you thought about more often or longer?
3. Was there something that surprised you, about the artworks themselves, or about your own reactions to those artworks?
 - a. Did you at any point have the feeling of: this isn't really something for me, or the exact opposite?

Connections with creative practice (concrete): 4. If you think of a specific visual choice you recently made during a project you're currently working on or recently completed — is there something from today that could have influenced that decision? Why or why not? 5. Were there specific elements of these paintings you'd want to experiment with / incorporate into your own work? What would that be, and what would that process/integration look like? 6. (Reference something specific they said earlier) Earlier you described [specific observation or reaction

from Phase 2 or 3]. How does that connect to how you normally think about your own creative choices?

Vocabulary and articulation: 7. Has looking at these works, in your opinion, given you new ways to describe or think about visual choices, whether those of the artists we looked at or your own? Why or why not? 8. Was there a moment today when you noticed something in a painting that you might not have noticed or paid attention to at the beginning of our conversation? What was it and why? 9. If you had to explain to a colleague or client why a visual choice works, how does that go for you now, and do you think this conversation has changed or added anything to that?

Broader reflection: 10. After today, what are your thoughts on actively engaging with historical art as part of (learning to) be a game artist? And is that different from what you thought before this interview? 11. Do you think what we discussed today says something specifically about you as a game artist, or would someone with a different creative background have had a similar experience? - Or: How do you think your being a game artist influenced your answers/interpretations today? 12. Is there anything else about your experience today, or about your (new) relationship to this kind of art, that you'd like to add?

Follow-up prompts (use where needed):

- Can you say a bit more about what that would look like in practice?
- What makes you say that?
- You mentioned [x] earlier. Has your thinking about that shifted?

Phase 5: Closing (2–3 minutes)

1. Is there anything about how we discussed the images today that you found useful or difficult?
2. Thank the participant.
3. Remind about data processing and withdrawal rights.
4. Offer to share findings.
5. Provide contact details.
6. Ask participants that if anything else comes to mind later, they're welcome to share it, to see how the information lands.

D.2 Follow-Up / Re-Interview Guide

Follow-Up Conversation / Re-Interview Guide

This conversation is an open, informal follow-up to the first interview. The goal is to further explore three themes: personal relationship with art, identity as a game artist, and practical application of traditional art. The questions are intended as conversation starters, not as rigid structure. Follow the participant.

Target time: 30–45 minutes

Opening, Looking Back (5–8 minutes)

Give a brief reminder of what you did last time. Explain that you're coming back because you wanted to further explore a number of things that came up then.

1. How did you actually find that first conversation? And has anything stuck with you afterward, a thought, an image, something you came across later?
 - a. Follow-up: Had you expected that to stay with you, or did that surprise you?
 - b. Follow-up: Has there been anything in your work or studies recently where you thought back to our conversation?

The Experience of the First Conversation, How Did It Feel (8–10 minutes)

2. If you think back to the moment just before you saw those paintings for the first time, what had you actually expected? How did you think it would be for you?
 - a. Follow-up: Was that right, or was it different from what you had thought?
3. What was it actually like to look at those paintings so intensively? Did that feel familiar, strange, or something else, and where do you think that feeling comes from?
 - a. Follow-up: Was there a moment when you thought: this appeals to me, or the opposite: this isn't really something for me?
 - b. Follow-up: Do you think that feeling says something about you specifically, or would everyone experience it that way?
4. Has our conversation sparked anything, in how you think about art, how you talk about it, or the desire to do more with it?
 - a. Follow-up: Or does it feel more like it confirmed something you already thought?

Art in Their Life, What Does It Mean to Them (8–10 minutes)

5. What does art actually mean to you, what do you get out of it? And which form of art do you mean when you say that?
 - a. Follow-up: Is that something you actively seek out, or does it come to you more naturally?
 - b. Follow-up: Does that also apply to traditional art, paintings, that kind of work? Or is that different for you?
6. What is traditional art to you, actually? How would you describe or define it?
 - a. Follow-up: Does what we looked at last time fall under that for you?

Identity, Who Are You as a Maker (8–10 minutes)

7. What label do you give yourself when you talk about yourself within this field? Do you feel like an artist, or not? And why?
 - a. Follow-up: Does that label change depending on who's asking, fellow students, family, someone outside the industry?
 - b. Follow-up: How do you describe to people outside the game industry what you make or who you are?

8. Do you feel there's a difference between you and an artist, someone who, for example, studies at a traditional art school? What would that be, if you had to name it?
 - a. Follow-up: Is that a difference in how you look, what you make, how you were trained, or something else?
 - b. Follow-up: Does that feel like something missing, something neutral, or something that actually belongs to who you are?
9. Do you think your being a game artist has influenced how you looked at those paintings last time, or how you look at art in general? In what way?
 - a. Follow-up: Would someone with a different creative background have looked at it differently, do you think?
 - b. Follow-up: Is that conscious, do you consciously look differently, or do you notice it more in retrospect?
10. How do you talk with fellow students or colleagues about visual choices in your work? Do you have a way of doing that, or is it more intuitive?
 - a. Follow-up: Is there a kind of shared language in your environment for discussing visual work, certain words, comparisons, references that everyone understands?
 - b. Follow-up: And how does that way of talking relate to how we talked about the paintings last time?

Practical Application, What Can You Do With It (8–10 minutes)

11. Can you give me a concrete example of how you normally process inspiration into your own work, preferably something recent? How does that process work for you? Or, alternatively: what do you use your inspiration material for, visual, narrative, something else?
 - a. Follow-up: Does it start visually, or does it start somewhere else?
 - b. Follow-up: At what point in your process do you look for references, and when do you stop?
12. Can you still remember what you mentioned last time as things you might want to experiment with? Is that still the case for you, or do you think differently about it now?
 - a. Follow-up: Can you now think of more examples of how you could use traditional art as a source of inspiration, concretely, in your own work?
 - b. Follow-up: Or is there actually something holding you back from doing that? What is it?
13. Do you have ideas about how traditional or historical art could have a place in a game art education programme? What would that ideally look like for you?
 - a. Follow-up: Is that something you yourself would have wanted, or do you see it more as something that could be useful for others?

Closing (3–5 minutes)

14. Is there anything you said in this conversation, or in our previous conversation, that you feel doesn't quite hold up, or that you'd phrase differently now?
15. Thank the participant. Remind them about data processing. Ask if they'd like to know what comes out of the research. Mention that if anything comes to mind later, they're always welcome to share it.

APPENDIX E

CONTEXTUAL NOTES (STAGE 3)

This appendix contains the brief contextual notes read aloud to participants during Stage 3, after their initial unprompted responses to each researcher-selected work. Each note covers the artist, title, date, and a short summary of historical context, drawn primarily from The Metropolitan Museum of Art's online collection entries. It is referenced in Section 3.5.2.

Image 1: Bathers — Paul Cézanne (1874–75)

This is *Bathers*, painted by Paul Cézanne, a French artist, between 1874 and 1875. Cézanne painted the subject of bathers repeatedly throughout his career. He rarely worked from live nude models, instead composing his figures from imagination and earlier studies, which is why the bodies in his bather paintings often have an unusual quality to them.

Image 2: Circus Sideshow (Parade de cirque) — Georges Seurat (1887–88)

This is *Circus Sideshow*, or *Parade de cirque*, painted by Georges Seurat, a French artist, in 1887 to 1888. It shows musicians and a ringmaster trying to attract an audience outside a travelling circus in a working-class area of Paris. Seurat developed a technique of placing small dots of pure colour next to each other, which became known as Pointillism. This is one of his first paintings of a nighttime scene lit by artificial light.

Image 3: Oleanders — Vincent van Gogh (1888)

This is *Oleanders*, painted by Vincent van Gogh, a Dutch artist, in 1888 while he was living in Arles in the south of France. Van Gogh painted this as an expression of joy and vitality during a period when he felt optimistic about his life and work there. The book in the painting is Émile Zola's novel *La Joie de Vivre*, which translates to "The Joy of Living."

Image 4: Still Life with Teapot and Fruit — Paul Gauguin (1896)

This is *Still Life with Teapot and Fruit*, painted by Paul Gauguin, a French artist, in 1896. At this point Gauguin had left France and was living in Tahiti, where he spent much of the last decade of his life. He continued to paint European subjects like still lifes alongside works depicting Polynesian life, often combining elements from both visual traditions.

Image 5: Steamboats in the Port of Rouen — Camille Pissarro (1896)

This is *Steamboats in the Port of Rouen*, painted by Camille Pissarro, a French artist, in 1896. Pissarro painted a series of views of Rouen's harbour from a hotel window, working on multiple canvases at once to capture different weather and light conditions. He was one of the older figures associated with both Impressionism and Post-Impressionism, and was known for mentoring younger artists including Cézanne and Gauguin.

Image 6: The Repast of the Lion — Henri Rousseau (ca. 1907)

This is *The Repast of the Lion*, painted by Henri Rousseau, a French artist, around 1907. Rousseau never travelled outside of France. He created his jungle scenes using studies made at the botanical gardens in Paris and by looking at images of animals in illustrated magazines and

children's books. He worked as a customs official, which is why he was nicknamed "le Douanier."

APPENDIX F

ORIGINAL DUTCH QUOTATIONS

This appendix provides the original Dutch-language source text for participant quotations that appear (or have appeared) in translated form in Chapter 4, presented for reference and verification. Full transcripts and recordings are not reproduced here and remain available to other researchers upon request, as noted in Section 4.4. It is referenced in Section 4.4.

Quote 1 — P7 English: “My sister is an artist. She’s a photographer, but really the artistic side, not necessarily of people. I think that’s had a really big influence on me, because she’s 10 years older than me, in a way she’s always been a bit of a mother figure. [...] I just notice that a lot of the ways I look at the world, I’ve maybe taken over from her a bit.” Dutch: “Nou, mijn mijn zus is kunstenaar. Het is fotografe, maar dan echt wel de artistieke kant op, niet per se van mensen. Dat denk ik, dat heeft ook wel echt heel veel invloed gehad op mij, want ze is 10 jaar ouder dan ik — op een bepaalde manier is altijd wel een moederfiguur geweest. [...] Ik merk gewoon dat heel veel manieren dat ik naar de wereld kijk dat ik dat ook al een beetje van haar misschien over heb genomen.”

Quote 2 — P5.2 English: “zweverig” (floaty, pretentious) Dutch: “het zweverige label ‘kunst’”

Quote 3 — P4 English: “Any toddler could do that for you. What’s so interesting about this?” Dutch: “Wij gaan elke kleuter kan dat wel voor je doen. Wat is hier nou zo interessant aan?”

Quote 4 — P4.2 English: “With this kind of painting work, I come in more negatively, I think unconsciously” Dutch: “Bij dit soort schilderijwerken kom ik meer negatief binnen, denk ik onbewust.”

Quote 5 — P2.2 English: “a destructive concept” Dutch: “Ik vind het, om het heel simpel te zeggen, een destructief concept.”

Quote 6 — P2.2 English: “The frustration of it - people who all act like they know what it is, and at the same time want to say that nobody actually really knows what it is.” Dutch: “De frustratie ervan wanneer je ervan. Mensen die allemaal doen alsof ze weten wat het is en ondertussen ook willen zeggen dat niemand eigenlijk echt weet wat het is.”

Quote 7 — P1.2 English: “For me, an artist is an individual who focuses a lot on the emotional level, whether that’s emotion from within themselves that they put into a work, or evoking emotion through their work, or simply wanting to give knowledge or insight about a specific subject. [...] And a designer, that’s more in my eyes a practical field where the real action is: something really needs to be made. It has a specific goal that needs to be maintained, and emotion isn’t always the point. Sometimes something simply needs to be there to be there.” Dutch: “Ja, voor mij is een kunstenaar een individu die veel focus op het emotionele vlak — of dat nou emotie is uit zichzelf en dat in een werk stoppen, of emotie oproepen uit hun werk, of simpelweg kennis of inzicht wil geven over een specifiek onderwerp. [...] En een ontwerper, dat is meer in mijn ogen een praktisch vakgebied waar de echte handeling is: er moet echt iets komen. Het heeft een specifiek doel wat behouden moet worden en emotie is daar niet altijd het punt van. Soms moet iets gewoon simpelweg er zijn om er te zijn.”

Quote 8 — P11 English: “The more emotion, the better I think it is” Dutch: “Hoe meer emotie, hoe beter ik het vind.”

Quote 9 — P11 (paraphrased) English: “a kind of connection with the artist, even though they’ve long been dead” Dutch: “Wat dan honderden jaren geleden is geleverd, maar iets wat mij wel verbindt met die tijd daar, daar krijg ik wel. Dat roept emotie bij me op.” / “een soort connectie met de artis, ook al is hij al lang dood.”

Quote 10 — P7 English: “I don’t really see myself as an artist. I think that’s maybe what I technically already am. But I feel that’s a title I won’t assign to myself, because the things I make just don’t have that much impact. They don’t really convey feeling. There’s no deeper meaning. It’s often just an image I enjoy making.” Dutch: “Ik zie mezelf ook niet als een kunstenaar. Dat vind ik zelf best wel wat ik misschien technisch gezien al ben. Maar ik vind dat de titel die ik niet aan mezelf zal toewijzen, omdat de dingen die ik maak die hebben gewoon niet zoveel impact. Die brengen niet per se gevoel over. Het heeft geen diepere betekenis. Het is vaak gewoon een beeld wat ik mooi vind om te maken.”

Quote 11 — P7 English: “She’s really an artist, but I just don’t see myself as an artist.” / “That’s something I’d want to look into. Just how you can make game art so that it’s more... that it’s really art instead of support for gameplay.” Dutch: “Zij is echt een kunstenaar, maar ik zie mezelf gewoon niet als een kunstenaar.” / “Dat is wel iets wat ik zou willen opzoeken. Gewoon hoe je game art gewoon kan maken zodat het meer dat echt kunst is in plaats van ondersteuning van gameplay.”

Quote 12 — P10 English: “I feel more like a maker than an artist. Because I just make things because I enjoy doing it. Not with the intention that it’s art.” / “Apparently. If someone considers that art and I made it, then in their eyes I’m an artist. Then my own perception doesn’t really matter anymore.” Dutch: “Ik voel me meer maker dan kunstenaar. Omdat ik gewoon dingen maak, omdat ik het leuk vind om te doen. En niet voor de intentie dat het kunst is.” / “Blijkbaar. Als iemand dat kunst vindt en ik heb het gemaakt, dan ben ik in hun oog kunstenaar. Dan maakt de eigen perceptie niet echt meer uit.”

Quote 13 — P9 English: “Yes, I design things, so then yes” / “No. Because ‘artist’ is so often seen as, at least I see it that way too, as a painter or something. Yeah, really that old traditional art.” Dutch: “Ja, ik ontwerp dingen, dus dan ja.” / “Nee.” / “Omdat kunstenaar heel vaak zo gezien wordt — in ieder geval ik zie het ook eigenlijk zo — als schilder of zo. Ja, echt dat oude traditionele kunst.”

Quote 14 — P1.2 English: “Also a bit ashamed, because you know, we’re going to talk about major works and I, even with an art academy background, can’t always name them. I also think: oh, I should really just know this.” Dutch: “Ook wel een beetje beschaamd, want weet je, we gaan het over grote werkstukken hebben en ik met ook een kunstacademie-achtergrond die werken niet altijd even kan benoemen. Ik denk ook van: oh, dit moet ik eigenlijk wel gewoon weten.”

Quote 15 — P11 English: “I knew it! Because he has those typical brushstrokes. But I thought: it looks so familiar. And I didn’t want to say it.” Dutch: “Ik wist het! Want hij heeft die typische brushstrokes, zeg maar. Maar ik dacht zo van: het komt me zo bekend voor. En ik wilde het niet zeggen.”

Quote 16 — P7 English: “I wanted to say right away, is this Van Gogh, but I also didn’t want to get it wrong by saying something completely incorrect.” Dutch: “Ik wilde gelijk zeggen van, is dit Van Gogh, maar ik wilde ook niet de mist in gaan door het compleet verkeerd te zeggen.”

Quote 17 — P4 English: “I had actually expected it to be one of those cases where I’d be told: oh, but you’re completely wrong, because that happens so often when you’re looking at art history things in school. It’s always: what do you see here? And you say: I see an apple. And then it turns out you’re totally wrong, because the apple supposedly stands for something else entirely” Dutch: “ik had eigenlijk ergens had verwacht dat het dan zo’n geval zou zijn waarin ik werd verteld. Zo van, oh, maar je bent totaal offerte, want dat heb je zo vaak met als je dus in de geschiedenisboeken aan het kijken bent voor je school dingen met de kunstgeschiedenis dingen... het is dan heel vaak zo van ja, wat zie je hier? En als er van, ik zie een appel. Wat moet ik nog meer zien?” *Note: Translation is paraphrased; Dutch transcript is fragmented.*

Quote 18 — P7 English: “A lot of game art programmes just don’t have, I don’t know, we just didn’t really have art lessons” Dutch: “Veel game art opleidingen, die hebben gewoon geen — ja, ik weet niet — wij hebben gewoon niet echt kunstles gehad.”

Quote 19 — P5.2 English: “I don’t need to know that much about this, so I can just have my opinion about it. I think it’s beautiful or I think it’s really ugly, without having to justify it. At the same time, when it’s something game-related, I sometimes feel: oh, I studied for this. I should be able to have a well-argued opinion about this.” Dutch: “Ik hoef hier niet zoveel van te weten, dus ik kan hier gewoon mijn mening over hebben. Ik vind het mooi of ik vind het echt lelijk, zonder dit te hoeven beargumenteren. Tegelijkertijd als het meer gaat om iets games-achtig, voel ik soms wel de: oh, ik heb hiervoor gestudeerd. Ik zou hier een beargumenteerde mening over moeten kunnen hebben.”

Quote 20 — P2 English: “I think in traditional art I’m mainly looking for unique things that when you look at them you suddenly think: oh yeah, that’s also an interesting way to look at something” Dutch: “Ik denk dat ik in de traditionele kunst voornamelijk op zoek ben naar unieke dingen die wanneer je er naar kijkt ineens denkt van, oh ja, dat is ook wel een interessante manier om ergens naar te kijken.”

Quote 21 — P11 English: “I immediately look at the models, how they’re drawn. It really looks as if he was just standing there in real life with his little painting. But that wasn’t the case. So I wonder whether he made this in some depressive dark attic room, or whether he was actually outside.” Dutch: “Ik kijk dan meteen naar de modellen hoe ze zijn getekend. Het lijkt heel erg alsof hij gewoon hier ook in het echt stond bij stond, zeg maar, dat hij gewoon erbij staat met zijn schilderijtje. Maar dat was dus niet zo. Dus ik vraag me af of die dat dan in een hele depressieve donkere zolderkamer gemaakt, of dat hij ook echt buiten was.”

Quote 22 — P7 (paraphrased) English: individual brushstrokes — “sometimes just a line” — creating immersive atmosphere Dutch: “beweging in. Ook al zijn die bewegingen soms maar een streepje. En daardoor voelt het een beetje alsof ik een soort van Ben alsof ik er echt in zit.”

Quote 23 — P1.2 English: “I find the works made by the artist themselves more meaningful. It feels closer, as if I genuinely have a piece of that artist hanging in my room, rather than just their work.” Dutch: “Bij elke penseelstreek die ze daarin gemaakt hebben, bij het werk — of bij elke keuze van kleur tot stroke van de pen of van het penseel — vind ik de werken die gemaakt zijn door de kunstenaar zelf wat meer zeggender. Het voelt wat dichterbij alsof ik gewoon echt een gedeelte van die kunstenaar in mijn kamer heb hangen, in plaats van alleen maar hun werk.”

Quote 24 — P5.2 English: “I think that art I find beautiful and can really appreciate automatically gives me a bit more of a feeling that I’m closer to it, because then I’m automatically somewhat interested in it.” Dutch: “Ik denk dat de kunst die ik mooi vind en veel

kan waarden automatisch een beetje meer het gevoel geeft dat je er dichterbij staat, want dan ben je automatisch wat geïnteresseerd erin.”

Quote 25 — P2.2 (paraphrased) English: as a game artist, encountering a familiar composition or technique prompts faster engagement Dutch: “Als game artist zal je twee keer sneller denken van: hé, dit zou of dit kan bijvoorbeeld dit aanduiden, of stel het is een bepaalde compositie die je herkent.”

Quote 26 — P6 English: “mainly for concept art on ArtStation, then I save it in a folder” Dutch: “Ik zoek vooral naar concept art of ArtStation, dan sla ik wel op in een folder.”

Quote 27 — P6 English: “He also thinks that a lot of modern game art looks very similar to each other, he really stands out” Dutch: “Hij vindt ook dat heel veel moderne Game Arts heel veel op elkaar lijken, zeg maar — hij steekt er dan wel inderdaad heel erg uit.”

Quote 28 — P1.2 English: “very blindfolded” Dutch: “heel erg geblinddoekt”

Quote 29 — P10 English: “because people there have more creative freedom to experiment without ten million stakeholders thinking it’ll blow their budget” Dutch: “Te experimenteren zonder dat 10 miljoen stakeholders vinden dat het hun budget opblaast.”

Quote 30 — P7 English: “Even if you deviate just a little bit from the norm, people already...” Dutch: “Als je ook maar een klein beetje afwijkt van de norm...”

Quote 31 — P9 English: “No. Neither of them [are relevant]” Dutch: “Nee. Nee, allebei niet.”

Quote 32 — P9 English: “We also have a particular style in our games, and it just doesn’t match with these 3 styles. [...] We draw digitally, and it all looks more realistically drawn. With these 3, you could just see that it was still a painting” Dutch: “Wij hebben ook een bepaalde stijl in onze games en dat matcht gewoon niet met deze 3 stijlen. [...] Wij tekenen digitaal, en het ziet er allemaal realistischer getekend uit. Dit zie je bij deze 3 — zag je gewoon dat het nog schilderij was.”

Quote 33 — P9 English: “No, this is how I’ve always looked at art” Dutch: “Nee, dit is hoe ik altijd naar kunst kijken.”

Quote 34 — P10 English: “I naturally always think: oh, how could you transfer this same texture digitally?” Dutch: “Ik denk natuurlijk wel altijd na van, oh, hoe zou je deze zelfde textuur kunnen overbrengen digitaal.”

Quote 35 — P2 English: “Maybe the right one, unconsciously? But so quickly, I can’t really imagine it” Dutch: “Die rechts misschien wel onbewust? Maar zo snel, ik hoop het niet echt voorstellen eigenlijk.”

Quote 36 — P2 English: “No, I don’t think so” Dutch: “Nee, dat denk ik niet.”

Quote 37 — P8 English: “They’re a lot of muddy colors, natural colours. But everywhere there are actually a lot of almost hidden little colours worked in, where you wouldn’t expect them” Dutch: “Het zijn heel veel muddy colors, zeg maar, natuurlijke kleuren. Maar overal zit eigenlijk heel veel bijna verstopte kleurtjes in verwerkt, waar je dat niet zo zou verwachten.”

Quote 38 — P6 English: “I also find the colour use of the shadow interesting, that purplish quality. That’s also something I sometimes add in my stylized work, purple shadows” Dutch: “Ik vind ook het kleurgebruik van de schaduw ook wel interessant, dat paarsige. Dat is ook iets wat ik wel eens bij mijn stylized werk ook wel eens toevoeg, paarse schaduwen.”

Quote 39 — P8 English: “I think this kind of painterly style is really cool, so in my process it’s still planned [...] I would absolutely love it if I could sometimes apply it” Dutch: “Dit soort painterly stijl vind ik dus heel cool, dus in mijn proces staat nog gepland [...] ik zou het ontzettend gaaf vinden als ik het soms zou kunnen toepassen.”

Quote 40 — P5.2 English: “The colours or the textures or something, see if you could use that, yeah, kind of weave the vibe of a painting into your visuals, see if you could get it to feel somewhat the same” Dutch: “De kleuren of de textures ofzo, kijken of je dat zou kunnen gebruiken — ja, een beetje de vibe van zo’n schilderij met visuals erin verwerken, kijken of je dat een beetje hetzelfde zou kunnen krijgen.”

Quote 41 — P10 English: “Basically looked at traditional painting: OK, which art movements were active in our non-fictional world at that time. And eventually that led to expressionism. And that was then used as inspiration for the game” Dutch: “Ja eigenlijk de traditionele schilderkunst gekeken naar OK welke kunststromingen waren er in onze niet-fictieve wereld toen actief. En uiteindelijk heeft dat zijn pad gebracht naar expressionisme. En dat is dan weer gebruikt als inspiratie voor het spel.”

Quote 42 — P5 English: “seek broader inspiration than the things I normally look up” Dutch: “Misschien wat breder inspiratie zoeken dan de dingen die ik standaard opzoek.”

Quote 43 — P7 English: “How can you become the best at what you do without knowing what other people make?” Dutch: “Hoe kan je de beste worden zonder te weten wat andere mensen maken?”

Quote 44 — P3 English: References to “complementary colours,” “plein air,” “shape language,” Venus pose *Note: Interview conducted in English. No Dutch original.*

Quote 45 — P9 English: “That ghostly thing standing behind that woman, I can see a little face in it” Dutch: “Dat wat spookt achter die vrouw staat — ik zie haar als een gezichtje erin.”

Quote 46 — P9 English: “Nicely free. They’re just naked in nature and nobody cares, because everyone is naked” Dutch: “Lekker vrij. Ze zijn gewoon naakt in de natuur en het boeit niemand, omdat iedereen naakt is.”

Quote 47 — P9 English: Asked what the word “interpretation” meant Dutch: “Interpretatie — oh, wat betekent dat ook alweer?”

Quote 48 — P9 English: “I don’t stand like every day” Dutch: “Die man in het midden die zo gek over zijn hoofd zit... het is niet zo sta ik niet elke dag.”

Quote 49 — P1.2 English: “There are so many elements that give the image so much more value, that actually get pushed to the side a bit, because I’m really looking at: OK, how can I go from this to that?” Dutch: “Er zijn heel veel elementen die het beeld zoveel meer waarde geven, die eigenlijk een beetje naar de zijkant geduwd worden, omdat ik inderdaad heel erg kijk naar: OK, hoe kan ik van dit naar dat gaan?”

Quote 50 — P1.2 English: “I really started to notice more things and understand: oh wait, it’s not that they just randomly put something down. It’s the periods that people themselves go through and how they can translate that into their work” Dutch: “Ik begon inderdaad veel meer dingen op te merken en te begrijpen van: oh, wacht — het is niet dat ze lukraak iets neerzetten. Het zijn de periodes waar mensen zelf doorheen gaan en hoe ze dat kunnen vertalen in hun werk.”

Quote 51 — P8 English: “The longer you think about it or are in conversation about it, the more things actually come up. Because when I go to museums, I often just look by myself and then everyone is quiet. So then it’s just your own thoughts, but I think by also getting questions, you start thinking more deeply about other things. So elements that you might not immediately come up with if you just look at it.” Dutch: “Hoe langer je erover nadenkt of in gesprek over bent, hoe meer dingen er eigenlijk naar boven komen. Want als ik naar musea ga, dan kijk ik vaak gewoon zelf en dan is iedereen stil. Dus dan zijn het meer alleen je eigen gedachten, maar ik denk door ook vragen te krijgen dat je over andere dingen nog wat dieper na gaat denken. Dus elementen waar je misschien zelf niet meteen op zou komen als je er gewoon naar kijkt.”

Quote 52 — P11 English: “And also that probing, I really liked that, because at first glance I don’t say that much, but when you really keep asking and keep looking, then it all comes up” Dutch: “En ook dat doorvragen, dat vond ik heel fijn, want in het eerste opzicht heb ik dan zeg je niet zoveel, maar als je echt verder gaat vragen en langer kijkt, dan komt het allemaal naar boven.”

Quote 53 — P6 English: “Especially with your second example, the circus, when I think about it for a long time, I started to deviate more from what the original idea was” Dutch: “Ik denk vooral bij jouw tweede voorbeeld met het circus doe ik er lang over na gaan denken — ging ik wel meer afwijken van wat nou het origineel idee was.”

Quote 54 — P5 English: “A little bit, but it’s been reinforced by having talked about it so much myself. Then you start to realise how interesting it can be to look at something for longer than two minutes, and that it can really add a lot” Dutch: “Een beetje, maar het is wel versterkt door het zelf ook zoveel over te hebben. Dan kom je er een beetje achter hoe interessant het kan zijn om nu langer dan twee minuten naar te kijken en dat het ook echt veel kan toevoegen.”

Quote 55 — P11 English: “I really liked that you could tell those stories afterwards, so that I could first look for myself. [...] In that way I do think: oh yeah, that sounds nice to do differently next time” Dutch: “Ik vond het wel heel fijn dat jij achteraf dus die verhalen kon vertellen, dus dat ik eerst zo van zelf kon kijken. [...] Op die manier denk ik wel eens van: oh ja, dat lijkt me wel leuk om dat anders te doen de volgende keer.”

Quote 56 — P1.2 English: “The scope stayed quite narrow and it does feel as though that’s been widened a bit, which I can also take into my own work. [...] I can now also use it as a reference point, as a looking-back point, as inspiration for work” Dutch: “Het vizier bleef vrij nauw en het voelt inderdaad wel alsof dat wat meer verbreed is, wat ik dan ook mijn eigen werk mee kan gaan nemen. [...] Ik kan het nu ook gaan gebruiken als referentiepunt, als terugkijkpunt, als inspiratie voor werk.”

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